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专业： 地理信息科学

年级： 地信 1811

姓名： 温恩泽

指导教师： 冯驰

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摘 要

随着水环境问题的不断出现,太湖的水环境变化渐渐成为人们关注的问题。叶绿素 a 浓度(Chlorophy-a, Chl-a)作为衡量水体水质的重要参数之一,常用来作为衡量水体富营养化程度的指示标准。本文根据太湖 2013 年 5 月 13 日一天 8 景 GOCI 影像对太湖的叶绿素 a 浓度进行反演,探讨太湖叶绿素 a 浓度的日间空间分布状况,分析太湖富营养水体的时空分布特征。本研究的基本流程如下:首先,下载 2013 年 5 月 13 日一天 8 景的 L1BGOCI 影像,将影像裁剪至太湖区域,并通过 6S 大气校正模型对 GOCI 遥感影像进行大气校正,详细阐述了基于 6S 的大气校正模型的参数设置以及校正过程;然后,探讨了比值叶绿素 a 浓度反演模型在遥感反演中的建立原理,并将该模型应用于 GOCI 影像太湖叶绿素 a 浓度反演中;最后,根据反演的结果从整体时空分布特征、日间叶绿素 a 浓度增长特征以及高值区分布三个方面分析 2013 年 5 月 13 日当日的太湖叶绿素 a 浓度变化特征。本研究旨在探讨提高叶绿素 a 浓度反演精度的方法以及叶绿素 a 浓度反演模型在实际中的应用,为日后太湖水体叶绿素 a 浓度的精确估算提供一定的参考价值。

关键词: GOCI 影像; 大气校正; 叶绿素 a 浓度; 反演; 太湖

Inversion of chlorophyll a concentration in Taihu Lake based on GOCI imagery

Abstract

With the continuous emergence of water environmental problems, the water environment of Taihu Lake has gradually become a widespread concern. As one of the most important water quality parameters, chlorophyll a concentration (chlorophyll-a, Chl-a) is often used as an indicator to measure the degree of eutrophication for inland lakes. In this study, the chlorophyll a concentration was retrieved from GOCI images of Taihu Lake on May 13th, 2013. The retrieved results can not only vividly reflect the spatial distribution of chlorophyll a concentration, but also reflect the transformation of chlorophyll a concentration in the water. The basic process of this study is as follows: Eight GOCI images on May 13, 2013 were downloaded from the corresponding website and cropped into the observation area. Firstly, atmospheric corrections are performed on the GOCI imagery using the 6s atmospheric correction model. The parameter setting and correction process of the atmospheric correction based on 6S were elaborated in detail. Then, the establishment of three-band Chl-a retrieval algorithm and its application in Taihu Lake based on GOCI images are discussed. Finally, according to the inversion results, the variation characteristics of chlorophyll a concentration in Taihu Lake on May 13th, 2013 are analyzed from three aspects: spatial-temporal characteristics, growth trend, and distribution of high-value areas. The purpose of this study is to explore the method of improving the accuracy of chlorophyll a concentration inversion and the application of chlorophyll a concentration inversion model in practice, and to provide a certain reference value for the accurate estimation of chlorophyll a concentration in Taihu Lake at different times in the future.

Keywords : GOCI image; Atmospheric correction; Chlorophyll a concentration; Inversion; Taihu Lake

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第1章 绪论

1.1 研究背景

太湖是中国五大淡水湖之一，地处长江三角洲腹地，横跨江苏，浙江，安徽，上海。近年来，由于人类活动的日益频繁，太湖富营养化程度日益严重，蓝藻在富营养化水域中大量繁殖，导致水华爆发。例如，无锡太湖地区发生大规模的蓝藻暴发，导致无锡市许多地方的自来水受到严重的污染，人们的饮水用水出现了严重的短缺。尽管国家采取了相应的措施，但是这次的“水华”事件对人民的生产和生活造成了很大的影响。因此，太湖及其周边区域的可持续发展受到蓝藻暴发所引发的一系列环境问题。特别是太湖地区的饮水、养殖、旅游等生态环境受到了极大的影响，不仅影响了太湖地区的经济、社会发展，而且还对周边居民的身体健康造成了极大的危害。近年来，国内外有关专家针对太湖叶绿素 a 浓度进行了一系列专门的研究，以应对太湖富营养化程度和与之相关的环境变化机理。例如，王珊珊等（2015）在《太湖水体叶绿素浓度反演模型适宜性分析》中，利用太湖 2007、2009、2011 年三年的实际水质参数和同步频谱资料，并与 MODIS、MERIS、GOCI、HJ-1 卫星 CCD 传感器的频段参数进行了比较，分别采用差值模型、比值模型、APPEL 模型等方法，对太湖的叶绿素进行了反演。朱冰川等（2020）在《基于 GOCI 数据的太湖叶绿素 a 浓度反演和蓝藻水华遥感监测》中采用了太湖 2019 年 6 月 3 日 GOCI 遥感资料，建立了太湖叶绿素 a 的反演模型，利用标准植被覆盖指数（NDVI）对其进行了研究。研究表明，在对 GOCI 遥感数据的反演中，比值模型相对于波段比值模型更加适用于太湖叶绿素 a 浓度的反演，最后依照反演结果进行太湖富营养化评价，发现富营养化程度随叶绿素 a 含量的变化趋势是一致的。郭宇龙等（2015）在《一种基于 GOCI 数据的叶绿素 a 浓度比值估算模型》中，利用标准比值算法结合实测资料，对 GOCI 三波段算法进行了改进，之后通过对三峡水库、巢湖、洞庭湖和太湖 289 个地区的叶绿素 a 值及光谱资料进行对比分析，得出了适用于内陆湖 GOCI 叶绿素 a 的模式。实验结果显示，GOCI 波段比值法是一种稳定、准确的方法，是一种具有应用

前景的方法。本文在阅读相关文献的基础上，采用了 GOCI 比值算法来实现太湖叶绿素 a 浓度的反演。

1.2 国内外研究现状

本文的研究领域主要涉及到内陆湖泊的水色遥感、大气校正模型以及叶绿素浓度反演算法三个方面。其国内外相关研究进展如下：

1.2.1 水色遥感

地球表面 71%的面积都被海水和其它水域所覆盖，从某种意义上说，海洋对人类的影响有限，但同时，它也给我们带来了全新的机会。大海中蕴藏着丰富的矿产、生物等丰富的资源，向海洋迈进是不可避免的。近几年，随着卫星和遥感技术的迅速发展，水体光学理论和生物光学特性的研究也得到了迅速的发展。其中，以光学遥感为基础的水体应用，也被称作“水色遥感”。利用水色遥感技术，可以提供海洋环境中生物分布、温度等基础信息，这对我们更好地理解海洋有着重要的意义。同时，海洋是一个非常复杂的环境，研究海洋的表面情况，可以帮助我们更好的观察和处理突发事件，提高人类的应急能力。海洋表面的浮游生物是海洋环境中的一项重要技术。因为海洋辽阔，所以总的浮游生物数量很多。研究显示，浮游生物可以有效的吸附 CO_2 ，并将其转变成有机物质，从而降低温室效应，使地球气温下降，从而提高地区的气候。通过研究发现，利用水-色遥感方法对海洋初级生产力进行了预测，与实测的海洋生产力具有很好的一致性，这说明了该方法的有效性。

水色遥感通常是利用水色卫星进行的，它是用于海洋遥感的专用卫星，同时也是用于水色遥感器的载体。根据水色遥感器的不同，其接收频带也不尽相同，但都是以可见至近红外线为主。根据其光学特性，可将其分为一类和二类。第一种水体的光学特性是由浮游生物和它的共生物质所决定的，其典型水域为开阔海域，以海洋为主。其典型特点是：沿岸环境及人为活动对其影响不大，水质相对稳定。第二类水体的光学特性以浮游生物、无机悬浮物、有机黄色有机物为主，典型的水域以港池为主，其

典型特点是与人类活动紧密联系,受多种人为因素的影响。水色遥测仪接收到的频谱信号是由大气散射、海面漫反射以及海面上的水辐射引起的。利用生物反演方法,可以获得水体中的叶绿素、无机悬浮、有机黄色等三个元素。

起初,水色遥感技术主要用于海洋水域,然而,由于内陆湖泊的生态环境问题越来越严重,因此,利用遥感技术对内陆湖泊进行了研究。近年来,我国的湖泊水色遥感发展迅速,尤其是在监测湖泊生态环境领域。以内陆湖泊的水华为代表,这是一种自然生态现象,藻类或浮游生物在淡水体内异常开花。这是由于人们的日常生活和工业生产过程中大量的氮、磷废水流入水中,从而导致了水体的富营养化。这时,水体中的主要植物有木霉属、微囊藻、鱼腥藻、小球藻属、隐球藻等,在水体中产生了大量的藻类,这些藻类在水体中呈现蓝、绿,部分水华是由甲藻和浮游动物造成的。水华通常会出现在内陆的湖泊、河流以及池沼中,对于人类的生产和生活也有着很大的影响。对于水华的研究,虽然不是对于内陆湖泊资源的开发问题,但是涉及到内陆湖泊灾害的预防,可以在经济生产中帮助我们趋利避害,更好的适应生活。况且严重的水华会改变湖泊系统的生态平衡,降低周边的环境质量,是人们应该密切关注的问题。

1.2.2 大气校正

大气的校正是指通过测量地面目标的总辐射强度,而不是实际地面的反射,它包括了大气对地面的吸收,特别是由散射引起的辐射误差。它是一种通过消除大气影响造成的辐射误差,从而对地面目标的真实表面反射率进行修正的一种方法。目前,大气的校正方法有统计型和物理型两种。由于地面参数与遥感资料具有一定的关联性,因此,该方法能较好地提取出局部区域的资料,例如:经验线性定标法、内部平场法等。如果最初的模式很糟糕,那么增加新的知识和信息会帮助我们了解如何改善模式,但是建立和了解这些物理模型的过程却是一段漫长而又曲折的历程。模型是从真实世界中提取出来的,因此真实的模型很复杂,包括很多变量,比如常见的6S模型,Mortran等。辐射校正是指在采集光遥感资料时,对辐射引起的各种误差(如辐射校正、大气校正)进行修正。其中6S模型以其开放源码、快速运算等优势得到了广泛应用。因此,本文以6S模型为基础对GOCIL1B影像进行大气校正和相关参数的调整。

1.2.3 叶绿素浓度反演算法

通过对叶绿素 a 浓度的反演,可以有效地反映出湖泊的生态状况,而随着叶绿素含量的反演技术的不断完善,目前,叶绿素 a 的反演主要有经验模型法、半经验法、半经验法和分析模型法。

首先,目前主要依靠的是经验模式,叶绿素 a 含量与遥感数据的相关性为研究对象,利用遥感技术反演了水体中的叶绿素 a 含量。利用观测光谱、水质、模拟数据等方法,计算出了叶绿素含量与光通量之间的关系,并利用所得到的公式进行反演。

其次是半经验/半分析模型,从上世纪 90 年代到现在,半经验/半分析模式是目前比较普遍的一种反演方法,它基于水环境中的电磁辐射传播过程,并将经验公式和辐射传递模型结合起来,运用理论和实证统计的方法对模型进行了描述。模型能较好地反映叶绿素 a 的含量。但是,在利用单一波段或波段波段进行反演时,一般都是三段式或先分类后再进行模拟,从而增加了计算的准确度。

最后是一个分析模型,该模型采用辐射传输模式,模拟了水体中的电磁波传播,并对其进行了生物光学建模,得出了叶绿素 a 的吸收系数和反向散射系数的关系,并用遥感数据反演了水体中的叶绿素 a 含量。

当然,不同的算法具有不同的优点和缺点,具体如下:

经验模型由于其算法成熟、过程简单而成为目前研究领域中的一个主要算法,但是由于其理论上的一些基本问题,以及一些具体的物理理论无法对其进行合理的描述。由于各区域的水质特点和频谱规律各不相同,无法对水体的全部情况进行精确的分析,也无法形成一个统一的经验反演模式。半经验/半分析模型是将水质的光谱特性与统计分析相结合的方法。它的物理机制和物理基础都很好,是可行的。这种方法在反演中误差不大,稳定性好,但是模型不具有很好的普遍性、过程复杂、模型的准确性。该模型具有很强的物理基础,无需大量现场观测资料,但其物理机制十分复杂,必须了解纯水、叶绿素、悬浮物、黄色物质等的光谱特征,建立分析模型非常困难。

表 1-1 叶绿素浓度反演方法的比较

反演方法	优点	缺点
经验模型	算法比较成熟、过程简单	缺乏物理依据
半经验/半分析模型	水质光谱特征与统计分析相结合，有一定的物理依据	对于精度要求较高的模型，过程比较复杂，普适性差
分析模型	有较强的物理机理、普适性好	模型构建难度大

1.3 研究的意义与目的

1.3.1 研究意义

叶绿素 a 是反映水体中藻类的生物量，是衡量和评价水体富营养化程度的一个重要指标。另外，随着卫星遥感技术的发展，各种模式可以用于不同特征的卫星图像，从而达到对内陆浑浊水体的遥感监测。GOCI 是全球首个海洋水色观测静止卫星，它日间每天 8 次的成像效率，是对水体遥感动态监测的一个重要基础。另外，GOCI 卫星的空间分辨率为 500 米，波宽为 20 nm，能较好地获取水体的空间特性和频谱特性，并能有效地改善计算结果，为进一步研究水体中叶绿素 a 含量提供了理论依据。

1.3.2 研究目的

本文采用了太湖 2013 年 5 月 13 日一天 8 景 GOCI 影像对叶绿素 a 浓度进行反演，并对叶绿素 a 的空间分布情况进行了分析，探讨了水体中叶绿素 a 浓度的时空变化规律。针对太湖 2013 年 5 月 13 日一天 8 景 GOCI L1B 影像，首先对研究区域的 GOCI 遥感影像进行大气校正，具体阐述了基于 6S 的大气校正模型的参数设置以及校正过程，实现对内陆水体的有效大气校正模型。然后，探讨比值模型在遥感反演中的建立以及在基于 GOCI 影像太湖叶绿素 a 浓度反演中的应用，最后根据反演的结果从整体时空分布特征、日间叶绿素 a 浓度增长特征以及高值区分布三个方面分析 2013

年 5 月 13 日当日的太湖水体中的叶绿素 a 含量变化特点, 目的在于探索提高叶绿素 a 浓度反演准确度的方法, 并将叶绿素 a 浓度反演模式用于太湖水体叶绿素 a 浓度的预测。

本文采用了太湖 2013 年 5 月 13 日一天 8 景 GOCI 影像对叶绿素 a 浓度进行反演, 并对叶绿素 a 的空间分布情况进行了分析, 探讨了水体中叶绿素 a 浓度的时空变化规律。本文针对太湖地区 2013 年 5 月 13 日一天 8 景 GOCI L1B 图像, 首先利用 GOCI 卫星遥感图像进行了大气校正, 并详细介绍了 6 S 模式下大气校正的参数设定和大气校正步骤, 从而实现了对内陆水域大气校正的有效模式。在此基础上, 对利用 GOCI 图像进行太湖叶绿素含量反演的研究, 从总体时空分布、日间叶绿素 a 含量的增加特征和高值区分布三个角度, 对太湖叶绿素 a 浓度的变化特征进行了分析, 目的在于探索如何提高反演叶绿素 a 的准确率, 并将叶绿素 a 浓度反演模式用于实际中, 从而为今后准确估计太湖各时段叶绿素 a 含量提供依据。

1.4 研究思路与技术路线

本文主要采用了 2013 年 5 月 13 日的 GOCI 一天 8 景 L1B 影像, 深入探讨了 GOCI 影像的大气校正算法。根据太湖地区卫星过境日卫星的实际观测情况, 利用 6 S 模式的大气修正模式, 对原始图像进行了大气修正, 模型的输入参数包括: 遥感器类型, 年代, 纬度, 气溶胶浓度和类型, 辐射条件, 特定波段和海拔高度, 地表覆盖类型和反射率。在此基础上, 结合太湖的地理位置及成像时间, 将其模式划分为中纬度夏季。太湖是一种弱吸收性的气溶胶, 也就是大陆型。通过大气修正后的数据, 得到了大气修正后的反射系数。从而精确地完成针对太湖区域的 GOCI 影像的精确大气校正, 为后续的遥感图像处理以及叶绿素 a 浓度的反演奠定基础。

在完成大气校正后, 建立叶绿素 a 含量的反演模型是必要的。利用 GOCI 卫星遥感数据, 建立了叶绿素 a 浓度反演比率模式, 在第四章中将参照相关反演模型实现对太湖区域的叶绿素 a 浓度反演, 并对反演结果进行分析和讨论。

1.5 论文组织结构

根据论文的研究内容和技术路线，共分五章：

第一章 绪论。本章主要论述了本文的选题背景和国内外有关叶绿素含量的遥感反演研究的最新成果，具体包括太湖叶绿素 a 浓度研究所涉及到的水色遥感、大气校正、叶绿素 a 浓度反演算法三个方面，最后则是主要阐述了研究的意义、目的、研究的具体思想及技术路线。

第二章 研究区概况与数据采集。第二章从地理位置、气候、环境等几个方面对研究区地理环境进行了简要的阐述，之后对本文的主要遥感数据 GOCI 影像作简单的介绍，包括其由来以及使用发展现状；最后则是对本研究所使用的 6S 大气校正模型的各个参数作具体的介绍与说明。

第三章 大气校正模型。作为数据处理的不可缺少的环节之一，大气校正对于后续遥感影像的分析及叶绿素 a 浓度的反演具有十分重要的意义。本章具体介绍了 6S 大气校正模型的方法和详细的大气校正过程，包括对相关参数的具体设置及具体操作过程。

第四章 基于 GOCI 影像的太湖叶绿素 a 浓度的反演。在完成大气校正后，即使用构建的 GOCI 比值模型对太湖中叶绿素 a 含量的反演以及对太湖叶绿素 a 日间时空变化的研究；本章还计算了太湖的富营养化程度时空分布特征，分析了太湖富营养化水体的具体分布特征。

第五章 总结与展望。对 6S 大气修正与叶绿素 a 反演的结果进行了归纳，并对今后的工作进行了展望。

1.5 本章小结

本章主要论述了论文的选题背景以及关于目前叶绿素 a 浓度反演研究进展的文献综述。根据太湖叶绿素 a 浓度研究所涉及到的水色遥感、大气校正、叶绿素 a 浓度反演算法三个方面的国内外研究现状。最后是本文研究的意义与目的、具体的研究思路和技术路线。

第 2 章 研究区概况与数据获取

2.1 研究区地理概况

太湖大致处于江苏省南部，北到江苏无锡、浙江湖州、江苏宜兴、江苏苏州，大致处于北纬 $30^{\circ} 55'40''\sim 31^{\circ} 32'58''$ 、东经 $119^{\circ} 52'32''\sim 120^{\circ} 36'10''$ 。它的西部和西南部是丘陵山区，东部主要是平原和水系。太湖位于中国的亚热带，具有温带、湿润的特点。夏季，由于热带海洋气团的作用，东南风在夏季出现。该地区的气候特征是：高热多雨；冬季受北方高压气团的影响；年平均温度在 $16.0\sim 18.0$ 之间，年降雨量在 $1100\sim 1150$ 毫米之间。此外，太湖地区也有着苏南地区特有的“梅雨”季节。

图 2-1 太湖地理方位图

太湖水体水质恶化，营养状况恶化，“水华”频繁出现。结果表明，湖中 N、P 含量明显高于富营养化和富营养化。根据氮、磷指标，太湖富营养化和富营养化面积超过 90%。近年来，无锡市太湖地区因富营养化程度高，近年来夏天蓝藻频繁繁殖，对水体造成了很大的影响。尤其在太湖地区发生大规模的蓝藻爆发，对无锡的水源造

成了严重的污染。国务院随即作出了重大指示，要求进一步加大对太湖的污染防治力度，江苏省也在加紧对太湖进行治理。

2.2 GOCI 影像数据

GOCI 是韩国最新一代的海洋水色遥测器，用于朝鲜和周边海域的海水颜色进行监控。GOCI 是韩国第一颗全球同步气象卫星 COMS，它是 2010 年韩国发射的第一颗全球同步气象卫星。GOCI 是 EADS-Astrium 公司开发的，它的主要任务是对朝鲜半岛周围海域的海洋环境进行监测，通过卫星可以对本地区的海洋生态系统进行长期和短期的监测，提供不断更新的遥感资料数据，如叶绿素、藻华含量或分布等数据。GOCI 重量大约 84 公斤，功率稍低于 100 W，大小 1.39 米*0.89 米*0.85 米。GOCI 具有很高的测量精度，它的辐射修正误差在 3.8% 以内，在 500 米的地表取样和 1 个小时的时间分辨率。另外，GOCI 光谱的频带选取与其在水色遥感中的应用相吻合。

表 2-1 GOCI 遥感影像 8 个波段指标

波段	中心波长/nm	波宽	观测重点
b1	412	20	黄色物质、浊度
b2	443	20	叶绿素吸光最大值
b3	490	20	叶绿素及其他色素
b4	555	20	浊度、浮游物质
b5	660	20	荧光信号、叶绿素、浮游物质
b6	680	20	大气校正、荧光信号
b7	745	10	气溶胶厚度、植被指数
b8	865	40	计算海上水蒸气量

为了反演太湖的叶绿素 a 浓度，获取太湖 2013 年 5 月 13 日当天叶绿素 a 浓度的变化规律以及水体富营养化状况。本文通过 OceanColor 网站获取了 2013 年 5 月 13 日当天的 GOCI 一天 8 景 L1B 影像，并对下载好的图像进行裁剪和大气校正，以便

后续的遥感图像的分析。

GOCI 数据的下载地址为: <https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/>。具体的下载方法如下:

1) 首先打开相应的网站, 注册个人账号

图 2-2 GOCI 数据查询界面

2) 在数据查询页面中勾选对用的 GOCI 选项并且选择所要下载影像的时间, 之后输入太湖所在区域的经纬度, 最后点击“find swaths”即可查询。

图 2- 3 GOCI 数据

3) 查询结果如图 2-3 所示, 之后下载所需要的一天 8 景影像图即可。

2.3 大气校正参数

2.3.1 卫星的几何条件

6S 模型在经过辐射校正后，首先输入的便是卫星的几何条件。本文对于卫星的几何条件应进行自定义，即输入太阳天顶角（Solar zenith angle）、太阳方位角（Solar azimuth angle）、卫星天顶角（Satellite zenith angle）、卫星方位角（Satellite azimuth angle）以及月、日。其中，太阳天顶角和卫星天顶角通过 SeaDAS 卫星属性数据（Global Attributes）查看，而太阳方位角以及卫星方位角则通过相关的网站进行计算。

卫星的几何条件无参数限制，参数名称为 `igcom`，取值范围为 0-7，具体取值及其对应含义如表 2-2。

表 2-2 卫星几何参数具体值

值	含义
0	use definition
1	meteosat observation
2	goes east observatio
3	goes west
4	avhrr (PM noaa)
5	avhrr (AM noaa)
6	hrv(spot)
7	tm(landsat)

2.3.2 大气模式

在 6S 模型中定义了多种大气模式，由于中国大部分地区都位于中纬度地区，所以在实际运用中，大气模式通常选用中纬度夏季或者中纬度冬季，仅有我国最南部的部分地区可以使用热带的大气模式。大气模式具体的模型代号即其含义如表 2-3 所示。

表 2-3 大气模式模型代号及含义

模型代号	含义
0	无气体的吸收(no gaseous absorption)
1	热带的(Tropical)
2	中纬度夏季(midlatitude summer)
3	中纬度冬季(midlatitude winter)
4	亚北极夏季(subarctic summer)
5	亚北极(subarctic winter)
6	北美标准 (us standard 62)
7	用户定义大气廓线 (34 层无线电探空数据) 包括: 高度 (km) 气压(mb) 温度(k) 水汽密度(g/m3) 臭氧密度(g/m3)
8	输入水汽和臭氧总含量水汽(g/cm2) 臭氧 (cm-atm)
9	读入无线电探空数据文件

2.3.3 气溶胶类型参数

在 6S 模型中定义了许多种类的气溶胶模型，在实际中使用最多的则是大陆型、海洋型、城市型等等。气溶胶类型参数无参数限制，参数名称为 iaer，取值范围为 0-11。具体参数及其含义如表 2-4 所示。

表 2-4 气溶胶类型参数

参数	含义	详细
0	无气溶胶	no aerosols
1	大陆模型	continental model
2	海洋模型	maritime model
3	城市模型	urban model
4	沙漠模型	shettle model for background desert aerosol

5	生物质燃烧型	biomass burning
6	平流层模型	stratospheric model
7	自定义	入体积百分比 (0-1) 灰尘 水溶型 海洋型 煤烟
8	自定义	多峰对数正态分布 (最多 4 种模式)
9	自定义	修正伽马分布
10	自定义	Junge 幂指数律分布
11	自定义	太阳光度计分布 粒子半径 (μm) 粒径分布 ($dV/d(\log r)$) ($\text{cm}^3/\text{cm}^2/\text{micron}$) 复折射指数的实部 nr 虚部 ni

2.3.4 气溶胶含量参数

在 6S 大气校正模型中，气溶胶含量参数限制为能见度必须大于 5 公里，参数名称为 v 。气溶胶的具体类型及其含义如表 2-5 所示

表 2-5 气溶胶含量参数取值

参数取值	参数含义
v	输入能见度
$V=0$	输入 550 纳米气溶胶光学厚度， $taer55=550$ 纳米气溶胶光学厚度
$V=1$	没有气溶胶

2.3.5 目标高度参数

6S 模型中需要输入目标的高度参数，其参数无参数限制，参数名称为 xps ，具体

的取值范围以及对应含义如表 2-6 所示。

表 2-6 目标高度参数

取值范围	含义
$xps \geq 0$	程序将目标认定为在海平面上的高度
$xps < 0$	输入目标地物的负的海波高度.

2.3.6 传感器高度参数

6S 模型中同时需要输入目标的高度参数，传感器高度参数无参数限制，参数名称为 xpp ，具体的取值范围以及对应的含义如表 2-7 所示。

表 2-7 传感器高度参数取值

取值范围	含义
$xpp = -1000$	卫星观测
$xpp = 0$	地面观测
$-100 < xpp < 0$	飞机观测

注：对于飞机观测，必须输入飞机和地面之间的水汽，臭氧含量和 550 纳米气溶胶光学厚度，如无数据则输入负值，水汽和臭氧根据 62 年美国标准大气内差，气溶胶则根据 2 公里指数廓线计算。

2.3.7 光谱参数

光谱参数虽然在整个波段计算气体透射率和散射函数，但处理强吸收波段吸收与散射的相互作用不精确，因此不适合强吸收带，参数名称为 $iwave$ 取值范围为 -2—70，具体参数值及其所代表的含义如表 2-8 所示。

表 2-8 光谱参数取值

参数	含义
-2	输入光谱范围的下限和上限 (μm)，滤光片函数为 1，输出文件中给出单色结果
-1	输入单色波长 (μm)，包括气体吸收
0	输入光谱范围的下限和上限 (μm)，滤光片函数为 1
1	输入光谱范围的下限和上限 (μm) 并输入滤光片函数 $s(\lambda)$ (间隔为 $0.0025\mu\text{m}$)
(2-70)	预定义卫星频段

2.3.8 地表反射率类型

地面反射系数是指没有被云和大气成分影响的地面反射系数。地面反射一般由辐射强度影像进行计算，其中包括辐射传递模式和 6S 大气修正模式。本文采用的为 6S 大气校正模型，其参数名称为 *inhomo*，取值范围主要是 0 和 1，具体含义如表 2-9 所示。

表 2-9 地表反射率参数

参数	含义
0	均匀表面 (HOMOGENEOUS CASE)
1	非均匀表面

2.3.9 激活大气订正方式

最后则需要输入大气校正参数以激活大气校正方式来实现大气校正。此参数无参数限制，参数名称为 *rapp*，一般都要根据图像的表光辐射亮度和反射率来激活大气订

正方式。其主要的参数值及其含义如表 2-10 所示。

表 2-10 大气订正参数

参数	含义
$rapp < -1$	不激活大气订正 (no atm. correction)
$rapp > 0$	输入表观辐亮度, 反演地物真实反射率
$-1.0 < rapp < 0$	输入表观反射率, 反演地物真实反射率

2.4 本章小结

本章主要是先从地理位置、气候以及目前的环境条件等方面简单说明了研究区的地理概况, 之后对本文的主要数据 GOCI 数据作简单介绍, 包括其由来以及现状, 最后则是对本研究所使用的 6S 大气校正模型的各个参数作具体的介绍与说明。

第3章 基于 GOCI 的大气校正模型

3.1 大气校正

3.1.1 大气校正的概念

对大气进行校正的目的是消除由大气散射引起的遥感图像的辐射误差。遥感技术利用各种辐射能与地球大气发生相互作用，使其产生的能量衰减，进而影响其光谱分布。大气衰减对不同波长的光有很强的选择性，因此，在不同的波段，大气的影像也会有差别。此外，由于目标与太阳的几何关系及穿越大气层的距离不同，造成各区域的图像灰度受大气的影晌，而同一地面物体的象素灰度在不同时间也会受大气的影晌。我们把这个现象叫做大气的校正。而且，即便是在正常工作状态下，收集到的数据也会有一些辐射错误。两种主要的环境衰减是由于大气的散射和吸收而导致的大气衰减，同时也导致了地面的衰减。然而，在所有的遥感应用中，没有必要对大气进行校正，往往会根据实际情况而定。

3.1.2 大气校正的目的

对大气进行校正的目的在于克服大气、光等因素对地表的反射效应。从广义上讲，是指地面目标的反射率、发射率、表面温度等物理模型的真实参数。从狭义角度看，大气的校正则是指获取地表真实的反射率数据，以消除大气中的水汽、氧气、二氧化碳、甲烷、臭氧等气体的反射，同时也能消除空气中的气体和气体的散射作用。大气修正主要是反映地面真实反射率的一种过程。

3.2 6S 大气校正模型

6S (Second Simulation Of The Satellite Signal in The Solar Spectrum) 是利用 FORTRAN 语言编写的，该模型主要用于太阳反射频带 (0.4-2.5 微米) 的大气辐射传播模式。在没有云层的情况下，在计算了臭氧、氧气、水汽、二氧化碳的吸收

和散射的基础上，考虑了气溶胶与地表的双向反射，以及目标高度、表面非朗伯体的特性以及新吸收分子的作用，采用了最新的近似计算方法，模拟了大气和气溶胶的吸收与散射。6S 大气校正模式的基本步骤是：先进行辐射校准，然后根据下列八个参数，依次将卫星的几何条件，大气模式，气溶胶种类，气溶胶成分，目标高度，传感器高度，频谱和反射率。最后，启动大气修正模式，生成的文件能够被输出。在进行大气校正前，首先需要对原始图像进行辐射校正。辐射定标的目标是确定遥感传感器在其相应视场中的数字量化数值（DN）与其相应视野内的辐射亮度值的定量关系。过程如下，对 L1B 的 DN 值进行辐射校正：

$$L = \text{scale} \times \text{DN} + \text{offset} \quad (1)$$

在式 1 中，L 表示辐射亮度，DN 表示已数字化的 L1B 数据，scale 表示转换的幅度，offset 表示转换的偏离。需要说明的是，GOCI L1B 影像在 2011 年 4 月份以后的数据，scale 的值为 10^{-6} ，offset 的值则为 0。

在上一章节中简单介绍了关于大气校正参数数据的获取，本章节对于大气校正参数设置过程作深入探讨，并使用 6s 大气校正程序完成大气校正。具体的 6S 大气校正过程如图 3-1 所示。

图 3-1 6s 辐射校正基本过程

3.2.1 卫星几何条件参数的设置

在进行大气校正时，首先输入的是卫星的几何条件参数，主要包括了太阳天顶角（Solar zenith angle）、太阳方位角（Solar azimuth angle）、卫星天顶角（Satellite zenith angle）、卫星方位角（Satellite azimuth angle）以及月、日。具体操作如图 3-2 所示。

```

GEOMETRICAL CONDITIONS:
-----
IGEOM is in the range 0-7, igeom = 0

YOUR OWN CONDITIONS:
-----
asol (solar zenith angle) = 23.89
phi0 (solar azimuth angle) = 226.77
avis (satellite zenith angle) = 41.80
phiv (satellite azimuth angle) = 183.12
month (month) = 5
jday (day) = 13
    
```

图 3-2 卫星几何参数设置

3.2.2 大气模式

本文研究采用的是 2013 年 5 月 13 日的 GOCI 一天 8 景遥感图像，此时太湖处于夏季，且太湖位于我国中纬度地区，根据表 2-2 可得参数值为 2。具体操作如图 3-3 所示。

```

ATMOSPHERIC MODEL:
-----
idatm (0-8) = 2
    
```

图 3-3 大气模式参数

3.2.3 气溶胶模式

输入气溶胶模式（城市型气溶胶、大陆型气溶胶），太湖选择大陆型，根据表 2-3，参数值为 1.具体操作如图 3-4 所示。

```

AEROSOL MODEL (TYPE).
-----
iaer (0-12) = 1
    
```

图 3-4 气溶胶模式参数

3.2.4 观测位置能见度或者气溶胶光学厚度

输入观测位置的能见度或者气溶胶光学厚度。若填写能见度,太湖夏季为 15 米;若填写气溶胶光学厚度,则通过以下 AERONET 网站查询当时当地的 AOD 550nm,其中观测站选择 Taihu,本文填写能见度。具体操作如图 3-4 所示。

```
AEROSOL MODEL (CONCENTRATION).
-----
v (visibility) = 15
```

图 3-5 观测能见度参数

3.2.5 传感器以及地面高程信息

输入传感器、地面高程信息:其中 GOCI 位置高度(sensor altitude)为-35837 千米。

```
XPS is to express the altitude of target.
xps (in km) = 0

XPP is to express the sensor altitude.
xpp = -358737
```

图 3-6 传感器及地面信息参数

3.2.6 波段选择

选择波段,其中 GOCI 波段分别为 412、443、490、555、660、680、745 和 865。其中,前五个波段每个波段的宽度为 20nm,后三个波段每个波段的宽度为 10nm。以 745nm 为例, wlinf 为 0.745, wlsup 则为 $0.42+0.01=0.755$ 。

```
ENTER THE SPECTRAL CONDITIONS:
-----
iwave (-1 to 34, see introduction for details) = 0
wlinf (sub-limit of the filter function) = 0.745
wlsup (sup-limit of the filter function) = 0.755
```

图 3-7 波段选择

3.2.7 地表反射率类型

输入地表反射率类型参数，根据表 2-8 可得参数值为 0，即均匀表面。

```
GROUNRD REFLECTANCE (TYPE)
-----
inhomo (0-1) = 0
idirec: idirec = 0, no directional effect; idirec = 1, has directional effect.
idirec = 0
igroun = 4
```

图 3-8 地表反射率参数

3.2.8 激活大气订正方式

最后激活大气订正，根据表 2-9 所示，此时需要输入大气校正激活参数。

```
RAPP is a parameter allows to activate atmosphec correction mode.
rapp = -0.2
```

图 3-9 大气订正

3.2.9 程序执行

在所有参数设置完成后，完整参数设置如图 3-10 所示。

```
■ E:\苏州科技大学 (本科下)\毕业论文\大气校正\环境遥感课程大气校正数据 - 副本\环境遥感课程大气校正数据 - 副本(GS)6s.exe
GEOMETRICAL CONDITIONS:
-----
IGEOM is in the range 0-7, igeom = 0
YOUR OWN CONDITIONS:
-----
asol (solar zenith angle) = 23.89
phi0 (solar azimuth angle) = 226.77
avis (satellite zenith angle) = 41.80
phiv (satellite azimuth angle) = 183.12
month (month) = 5
jday (day) = 13
ATMOSPHERIC MODEL:
-----
idatm (0-8) = 2
AEROSOL MODEL (TYPE).
-----
iaer (0-12) = 1
AEROSOL MODEL (CONCENTRATION).
-----
v (visibility) = 15
XPS is to express the altitude of target.
xps (in km) = 0
XPP is to express the sensor altitude.
xpp = -358737
ENTER THE SPECTRAL CONDITIONS:
-----
iwave (-1 to 34, see introduction for details) = 0
wlinf (sub-limit of the filter function) = 0.745
wisup (sup-limit of the filter function) = 0.755
GROUNRD REFLECTANCE (TYPE)
-----
inhomo (0-1) = 0
idirec: idirec = 0, no directional effect; idirec = 1, has directional effect.
idirec = 0
igroun = 4
RAPP is a parameter allows to activate atmosphec correction mode.
rapp = -0.2
```

图 3-10 大气校正过程

执行 6s 程序获得 sixs.out 文件，图 3-11 即为对目标卫星波段的大气校正数据，其中最下方 x_a 、 x_b 和 x_c ，即为对辐亮度 L 进行校正的参数，利用校正过后的系数方求出了遥感反射率。

$$y = \chi_a \times L_i - x_b \quad (2)$$

$$\rho = y / (1 + \chi_c \times y) \quad (3)$$

上式中， L_i 为波段辐射亮度， ρ 为校正后反射率。

```

*****
*                               atmospheric correction result                               *
*                               -----                                                  *
*   input apparent reflectance      :      .200                                          *
*   measured radiance [w/m2/sr/mic] :      72.535                                       *
*   atmospherically corrected reflectance :      .201                                       *
*   coefficients xa xb xc          :      .00333   .03728   .08088   *
*   y=xa*(measured radiance)-xb; acr=y/(1.+xc*y) *
*****
    
```

图 3-11 以 745nm 大气校正获得的 sixs.out 文件

3.3 结果分析与检验

在大气校正后的遥感图像验证中，应考虑视觉效果，空间细节和光谱信息保持。虽然目视效果可能差异不大，通过观测资料与相应的大气修正后的 GOCI 资料进行对比和分析。结果表明，采用 6 S 大气修正后的卫星遥感图像与实际观测资料比较相近，其各个波段的平均相对误差如表 3-1 所示。

表 3-1 大气校正前后的平均相对误差

波段	中心波长/nm	平均相对误差/%
b1	412	13.2
b2	443	8.66
b3	490	6.67
b4	555	15.17

b5	660	13.7
b6	680	12.99
b7	745	10.9
b8	865	13.89

从表 3-1 可以明显看到大气校正前后的差别，6S 模型操作过程复杂，但可以保持数据的真实性，从而可以满足叶绿素 a 浓度反演的要求。

3.4 本章小结

作为数据处理的不可缺少的环节之一，大气校正对于后续遥感影像的分析以及对于本研究内容具有十分重要的意义。所以本章具体介绍了 6S 大气校正模型的方法和详细的过程，包括对相关参数的具体设置以及操作过程。

第4章 太湖叶绿素 a 浓度反演和富营养化评价

4.1 GOCI 影像的太湖叶绿素 a 浓度的反演

本研究采用标准比值模型对 GOCI 影像数据的叶绿素 a 浓度反演模型。对于本文的太湖叶绿素 a 的 GOCI 遥感数据来说，选用 b6、b7 进行统计分析然后拟合的方法建立比值模型，模型构建如下：

$$y = 125.274x - 31.016 \quad R^2 = 0.450 \quad (4)$$

$$x = b7/b6 \quad (5)$$

下面根据上述模型对叶绿素 a 浓度进行反演，其中 b6、b7 分别代表 GOCI 影像的 680nm、745nm。

根据公式(5)和(6)所构建的叶绿素 a 浓度的反演模型，对太湖 2013 年 5 月 13 日一天 8 景 GOCI 遥感影像进行叶绿素 a 浓度的反演，以 11:00 时的反演结果为例，结果如图 4-1 所示。

图 4-1 2013 年 5 月 13 日太湖 11:00 时叶绿素 a 浓度分布图

从图 4-1 中我们可以得知在上午 11:00 时，对于太湖整体而言，当日叶绿素 a

浓度呈现从湖外围向湖中心减小的趋势。尤其是位于太湖北部的竺山湾、梅梁湾、贡湖湾北部水体以及部分沿岸水体影像偏红，代表这些地区此时叶绿素 a 浓度相对较高。

4.2 太湖叶绿素 a 浓度的日变化分析

本文在基于大气校正后 2013 年 5 月 13 日的一天 8 景 GOCI 太湖遥感影像图基础上在完成叶绿素 a 浓度反演，得出当日时间 8:00-15:00 八个时段太湖叶绿素 a 浓度的时空变化图，如图 4-2 所示。

图 4-2 2013 年 5 月 13 日一天 8 景时刻太湖叶绿素 a 浓度空间分布图

综合当日的一天 8 景 GOCI 影像图分析 2013 年 5 月 13 日当日的太湖水体中叶绿

素 a 的日变化，总结如下：

首先，总体上太湖叶绿素 a 含量总体呈上升趋势，与太湖中部湖区、太湖以南、竺山湾、梅梁湾、贡湖湾等湖区相比，叶绿素 a 含量较高。

其次，太湖中部地区和太湖以南地区的增长趋势更为明显。对于太湖北部的贡湖湾湖区，其在 8:00 时叶绿素 a 浓度仅 $15\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ ，而在 12:00 时已经达到了 $100\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ 左右，其中在 10:00-11:00 这个时间段内增长速度最快。与此同时，太湖中心湖区以及西侧、南湖区的增长显著，在 8:00 或者 9:00 时左右，湖心以及湖西侧绝大地区叶绿素 a 浓度仅为 $5\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ ，但是到 12:00，浓度已经达到了 $35\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ 。

最后，就高值区而言(叶绿素 a 浓度 $>100\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)，主要分布在太湖的边缘、北部和东部，这是由于受当日的天气情况的影响造成的。当日太湖为东南风，风力在 3-4 级左右，由于风的作用，南部湖区的藻类被驱散到太湖北部的梅梁湾以及竺山湾，最终形成了高值区大都分布在北部的分布格局。

4.3 太湖富营养化程度日变化分析

湖泊的富营养化是由于过量地吸收了氮、磷等营养素，造成水体中藻类及其它浮游生物的异常繁殖，使水中溶解氧含量下降，造成水质恶化，鱼群及其它动物大量死亡，而富营养化是现代湖泊富营养化的主要原因。其富营养化的主要原因是：工业废水和生活污水中的氮、磷等营养元素含量较高。通过直接或间接排放到湖中。此外，湖上的船舶和湖中的观光活动等排入湖中的废弃物，以及在水产养殖过程中所投下的鱼饵，以及周边农田施用农药、化肥、通过地面径流进入湖中等，都是造成富营养化的主要因素。当湖水富含养分的时候，一些蓝藻、绿藻、硅藻等浮游植物就会在湖面上形成一层厚厚的海藻，也就是所谓的“水华”。这对湖泊的水环境和生态环境造成了很大的影响。

太湖作为中国五大淡水湖之一，其富营养化问题一直影响着太湖及周边地区的环境以及经济发展。为了更好地了解太湖的富营养化程度，根据上文针对太湖叶绿素 a 浓度反演的结果，对太湖 2013 年 5 月 13 日一天做富营养化程度的日变化分析。为了

方便研究，本文采用了李云梅等(2006)建立的湖泊富营养化评价综合指数模型评价太湖富营养化水平，具体模型如下：

$$TLI = 10 \times (2.5 + 1.086 \ln C) \quad (6)$$

式(7)中，TLI 为富营养化综合指数；C 为叶绿素 a 质量浓度，ug/L。营养化标准为：TLI≤30 为贫营养、30<TLI≤50 为中营养、50<TLI≤60 为轻度富营养、60<TLI≤70 为中度富营养、TLI>70 为重度富营养。

表 4-1 富营养化标准

营养化指数范围	营养化标准
TLI≤30	贫营养
30<TLI≤50	中营养
50<TLI≤60	轻度富营养
60<TLI≤70	中度富营养
TLI>70	重度富营养

从太湖富营养化程度分布图来看，当日的富营养化指数都在 50 以上，主要是轻度富营养、中度富营养以及重度富营养三种。由于富营养化程度与叶绿素 a 浓度是紧密相关的，因此从太湖整体的空间分布来看，太湖富营养化水平总体呈边缘相对较高、北部高南部低、西部低东部高德趋势。从当天的太湖富营养化水平来看，其富营养化水平明显加剧，轻富营养区面积急剧减小，而中度营养区明显增加，重营养区也有部分增加。尤其是对于太湖中部而言，可以明显地观察到中部逐渐由绿色变为黄色，即中部的中度营养区不断地增加。

图 4-3 2013 年 5 月 13 日太湖富营养化水平分布图

4.4 本章小结

本章在大气校正完成后，建立了 GOCI 比值的叶绿素 a 反演模型，然后利用

GOCI 比值模型反演太湖中的叶绿素 a 浓度，再根据太湖叶绿素 a 的空间分布，进行叶绿素 a 浓度的日变化以及当日的富营养化程度的分析。

第 5 章 总结与展望

5.1 总结

本文获取太湖 2013 年 5 月 13 日太湖一天 8 景 GOCI 影像后,对影像进行精确大气校正后使用了比值模型算法对太湖叶绿素 a 浓度进行了反演,并根据反演的结果对太湖叶绿素 a 浓度作日变化分析,总结出当日太湖叶绿素 a 浓度变化的特点。为了保证 GOCI 影像数据在太湖叶绿素 a 浓度反演的精确性,首先研究了基于 GOCI 影像的 6S 大气校正算法,根据太湖当日的客观情况和图像的实际波段,获得了卫星的几何条件、大气模型、气溶胶类型参数、气溶胶含量参数、目标高度参数、传感器高度参数、光谱参数和表面反射率类型,最终通过 6S 程序完成大气校正,获取到 GOCI 影像数据精确地遥感数据。最终在大气校正的基础上对 2013 年 5 月 13 日一天以 1 小时为时间分辨率的一天 8 景图像做叶绿素 a 浓度反演,并且分析了太湖水体叶绿素 a 浓度在一天之内的变化特征。具体结论如下:

首先是大气校正,根据太湖当日的客观情况得出大气校正所需要设置的参数值,主要包括卫星的几何条件、大气模型、气溶胶类型参数、气溶胶含量参数、目标高度参数、传感器高度参数、光谱参数和表面反射率类型参数等。其中卫星几何条件包括了太阳天顶角(Solar zenith angle)、太阳方位角(Solar azimuth angle)、卫星天顶角(Satellite zenith angle)、卫星方位角(Satellite azimuth angle)以及月、日。太阳天顶角和卫星天顶角通过 SeaDAS 卫星属性数据(Global Attributes)查看,而太阳方位角以及卫星方位角则通过相关的网站进行计算。此外,由于太湖此时处于夏季且为中纬度地区,即大气模式为中纬度夏季。气溶胶模式选择大陆型、观测位置能见度为 15m,传感器以及地面高程为-35837km。最后选择相应波段,激活大气校正,最终完成对 GOCI 影像的大气校正。

其次是叶绿素 a 浓度反演模型构建,本文采用了先是构造和改进的比值模型,之后依据改进后的比值模型对太湖叶绿素 a 浓度进行反演,得出最终太湖叶绿素 a 浓度的分布图。

最后是关于 2013 年 5 月 13 日的叶绿素 a 浓度一天 8 的日变化分析特征,从整体特征、增长趋势以及高值区分布三个方面具体论述了当日叶绿素 a 浓度在太湖的分布特征,同时也对该天的营养化水平做了分析与评价。

5.2 展望

由于研究时间、技术手段、数据、作者自身的研究水平等因素,本文尚有许多有待深入研究和扩展的地方:

首先是采集资料,以 2013 年 5 月 13 日一日的 GOCI 8 个区域为例,由于水体中的叶绿素含量一直在变化,所以用相邻时刻的观测资料与最近一次成像时间的图像资料进行比较,往往会有一定的误差。因为地球同步卫星影像提供者的局限,所以只能在一天内的不同时段得到这些影像。太湖叶绿素含量在一日中各季节、不同生长阶段的变化特点还有待进一步的研究。

其次是关于大气的校正模式的运用,目前使用的是 GOCI 数据在进行大气的校正中所常常使用的 6 S 模式。大气的校正一直以来都是遥感图像中的一个重要问题,GOCI 数据是一种新型的水色遥感数据源,对其进行大气校正的方法尚不完善,而对 GOCI 数据的大气的校正问题将直接影响到 GOCI 影像的光谱匹配和最后的反演精度。

最后是叶绿素 a 浓度反演模型的构建,本文采用了比值模型进行叶绿素 a 浓度的反演,但是由于只是进行了单一的方法对叶绿素 a 浓度进行反演,无法确保此方法为最佳方法,要找出最佳适宜的反演方法,还需要运用其他的反演算法,如三波段比值算法,通过比较的得出最佳的方法。

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附录 A 译文

极浑浊二类水体(中国太湖)

遥感反射率模拟和叶绿素 a 浓度反演

摘要: 在光学复杂的二类水体中, 准确评估叶绿素 a (Chla) 浓度和通过遥感正确识别藻华以前一直是一个巨大的挑战。在本文中, 我们利用一个大型生物光学数据集来模拟中国太湖中一个极其浑浊和生物生产力的湖的遥感反射率。概念三波段模型 $[R_{rs}^{-1}(\lambda_1) - R_{rs}^{-1}(\lambda_2)] \times R_{rs}(\lambda_3)$ (其中 R_{rs} 表示水面上方的遥感反射率) 对检索 Chla 浓度进行了校准和验证, 并获得了对其准确性的详细评估。从 2006 年到 2007 年在 50 个地点收集了四个季节的水样, 涵盖不同的生态系统类型, 含有三种非常可变的光学活性物质 (浮游物是 $7.9\text{--}281.7 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, 叶绿素 a 含量为 $4.0\text{--}448.9 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, 湖泊中有色溶解性有机物 $[a_{CDOM}(440)]$ $0.27\text{--}2.36 \text{ m}^{-1}$). Secchi 圆盘的透明度范围从 8 到 85 厘米。检索精度 (r^2) 的最优三波段模型和相关带比法分别为 0.94 和 0.92, 而均方根误差 (RMSE) 和相对误差 (RE) 为 15.1 马克杯中点 L^{-1} (37.3% 占平均值) 和 18.0 马克杯中点 L^{-1} , 分别为 44.4% 和 60.2%。使用 MERIS 中心带的三波段模型的应用 $[R_{rs}^{-1}(681) - R_{rs}^{-1}(709)] \times R_{rs}(754)$ 还允许精确估计 Chla, 使用 r^2 、RMSE 和 RE 为 0.92, 17.0 马克杯中点 L^{-1} 和 48.1%。建立一个简单而强大的生物光学模型, 具有高检索精度和已知的误差预算, 将有助于利用原位和卫星遥感技术快速、准确和实时地评估藻华。

关键词: 吸收系数、叶绿素 a (Chla)、 误差预算、太湖、遥感反射率

1 引言

在过去 20 年里，工业发展、人口增长和土地利用变化导致养分负荷增加，导致中国太湖富营养化和浮游植物浓度增加。近年来夏季，地表堆积蓝藻微囊藻的大量繁殖阻碍了无锡和吴泾等大城市的饮用水厂的正常运行，从 5 月到 10 月，湖中梅良湾和珠山湾的蓝藻浓度尤其高。特别是在 2007 年 6 月初，贡湖湾的蓝藻水华污染了无锡市最大的饮用水工厂，导致无锡市供水中断了好几天。此外，由于微囊藻的毒性，特别是在夏季，太湖的蓝藻水华对健康构成了额外的潜在风险。暴露于有毒的微囊藻可导致野生动物、牲畜和水生生物的肝功能衰竭，以及人类疾病和死亡。有报道认为，我国东部地区人原发性肝癌的发病与饮用水中发现的微囊藻毒素[3]、[4]有关。

传统的叶绿素 a (Chla)监测方法在太湖的监测效果有限，只能提供固定游程中 Chla 浓度的空间分布数据。这种传统的舰载水取样计划的时间和空间限制并不足以报告浮游植物生物量的变化。这在水华条件下尤其成问题，此时浮游植物密度的变化率特别高，积累发生在短至几个小时或一天之内的时间周期，以及由于风浪的频繁扰动。2007 年无锡市供水严重污染的原因是常规采样频率低、采样面积小，未能识别出藻华堆积和沉积。

为了减轻藻华的影响，并对太湖饮用水厂发出警告，有必要利用更详细、更有效的技术对藻华的发展和运动进行检测、监测和预测。在一些沿海和湖泊水域，使用机载和卫星遥感已证明可以提供关于水质和蓝藻水华程度的更可靠的时空信息，而不是传统的监测[5] - [9]。因此，太湖采用了这种方法。

太湖是一个具有高度空间异质性的的大型富营养化浅水湖泊;不同的生态系统类型(藻类为主、大型植物为主、过渡区);浮游植物、颗粒物质和显色溶解有机物(CDOM)的复杂动态变化以及可变的生物光学特性[10] - [12]。由于遥感技术能够解析光学重要组分的陡峭空间梯度和时间变化，因此遥感技术是研究太湖浮游植物动态和水质管理的一个潜在的强大工具。然而，尽管有这样的潜力，这种方法还没有得到广泛的应用，而且对太湖三种光学活性物质(tripton、浮游植物和 CDOM)的生物光学性质和浓度的时空变化特征尚不清楚。因此，目前的研究主要集中在基于遥感反射率[13]、[14]

原位测量的光活性物质数据的收集上。针对这一需求，本文的研究目标如下:1)比较三种光活性物质在不同季节的浓度和光谱吸收系数的变化;2)建立遥感反射率模型并讨论其光谱特性;3)优化三波段模型估算 Chla 浓度;4)描述了检索模型的误差预算。

2 材料和方法

2.1 研究地点和抽样时间表

在湖泊不同区域的 50 个地点进行了光学测量和水样采集:样带 2(样带 17- 29)起源于公湖湾, 向西南延伸穿过湖心;样带 3(样带 30 -40)起源于广湖湾, 向西南延伸穿过湖心;和横断面 4(样带 41 -50)起源于 Xukou 湾和扩展整个湖西南,西山岛南部的传递(图 1)。测量和水四个季节邮轮上采集标本:冬天(2006 年 1 月 7 日 9 日)、弹簧(2007 年 4 月 25 日 27 日),夏季(7 月 28 日 2006 年 8 月 1 日),和秋天(2006 年 10 月 12 日 15 日)。

为了验证用于估计 Chla 浓度的三波段模型和波段比方法, 从 2005 年 5 月(17 19)和 10 月(16 18)的两次采样巡航中获得了独立的数据集(32 2 = 64 个样本)。这些调查的样点在太湖上基本均匀分布[15]。

图 1 样带和取样地点的分布

2.2 样品处理

Chla 样品用 Whatman GF/C 玻璃纤维过滤器过滤。用乙醇(90%)在 80℃下提取 Chla 和 phaeophytin a (Pa), 在 750 和 665 nm 下进行分光光度分析, 并对 Pa 进行校正。

为了获得总悬浮物(TSM), 水样通过预先燃烧的 Whatman GF/C 玻璃纤维过滤器 (450℃4h)过滤去除悬浮物, 干燥(105℃4h), 并称重。过滤器在 450℃下重新燃烧 4 小时, 再次称量以获得无机悬浮物(ISM)。TSM 减去 ISM, 得到有机悬浮物。为了从总颗粒干重中分离出非生物性浮游物的干重, 在实验室中对太湖优势种微囊藻 (Microcystis)和栅藻(Scenedesmus)进行培养, 测定其在不同生长期的干重、Chla 和 Pa 浓度。在平静的天气条件下收集表面藻华样本, 并使用蒸馏水清除, 以获得相对纯的浮游植物。然后, 将样品置于黑暗条件下。每 3 天采集样品, 测量干重、Chla 和 Pa 浓度。我们发现一个简单的线性方程可以描述浮游植物干重与 Chla 和 Pa 浓度之和的关系, 即:

$$C_{\text{phytoplankton}} = 0.09C_{\text{Chla+Pa}} (r^2 = 0.98, n = 31, p < 0.001) \quad (1)$$

其中, $C_{\text{phytoplankton}}$ 为浮游植物的干重, $C_{\text{Chla+Pa}}$ 为 Chla 和 Pa 浓度之和。由 TSM (C_{TSM})与浮游植物干重($C_{\text{phytoplankton}}$)的差值得到非生物性浮游物 (C_{Tripton})的浓度。

2.3 遥感反射率和固有光学特性的测量

使用 ASD 场光谱仪 (Analytical Devices, Inc., Boulder, CO) 进行下降流辐射度和上升流总辐射度的测量, 其光谱响应范围为 350 1000 nm, 光谱分辨率为 3 nm。采用水面法测定水面光谱[16]。将光纤安装在远离船体的底座上的最低点, 以减少船舶反射系数对采集光谱的影响。在晴空条件下, 在离水面约 0.3 米的高度测量参考面板、水面和天空的辐射光谱。在每个采样点测量相关光谱 10 次, 以优化信号-噪声比, 从而减少现场测量的误差。每个光谱都是从 90 个方位的太阳和从 40 度的最低点观看。离水辐亮度 $L_w(\lambda, \theta)$ 可以从以下公式得到:

$$L_w(\lambda, 0^+) = L_{sw}(\lambda, 0^+) - r_{sky} \cdot L_{sky}(\lambda) \quad (2)$$

其中 $L_{sw}(\lambda, 0^+)$ 为水面上涌辐亮度, $L_{sky}(\lambda)$ 为相同方位角、40° 天顶角下测得的天空辐亮度。 r_{sky} 是空气-水界面上天窗的镜面反射率, 在风平浪静时为 0.022, 风速高达 $5 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ [16] 时为 0.025。本文使用的常量值为 0.0245。

通过测量朗伯基准板 $L_p(\lambda, 0^+)$ 的辐照度, 得到了入射下沿辐照度 $E_d(\lambda, 0^+)$:

$$E_d(\lambda, 0^+) = \pi L_p(\lambda, 0^+) / \rho_p(\lambda) \quad (3)$$

其中 $\rho_p(\lambda)$ 是已精确校准到 30% 的参考板的反射率。

水面上方的遥感反射率 $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^+)$ 计算为出水上升流辐射亮度 $L_w(\lambda, 0^+)$ 与入射下升流辐射亮度 $E_d(\lambda, 0^+)$ 的比值。一些 $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^+)$ 光谱被排除在厚藻华或大型植物的数据集之外。本文获得了 176 个 $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^+)$ 光谱。

总吸收系数为 $a_{triton} [a_d(\lambda)]$ 、浮游植物 $[a_{ph}(\lambda)]$ 、CDOM $[a_{CDOM}(\lambda)]$ 和纯水 $[a_w(\lambda)]$ 系数之和。

$$a(\lambda) = a_d(\lambda) + a_{ph}(\lambda) + a_{CDOM}(\lambda) + a_w(\lambda) \quad (4)$$

本文采用 Smith 和 Baker 提出的纯水吸收系数 $a_w(\lambda)$ 。利用定量过滤技术 [18] 测定了 $a_p(\lambda)$ (包括 tripton 和浮游植物在内的总颗粒物的吸收系数)、 $a_d(\lambda)$ 和 $a_{ph}(\lambda)$, 其中甲醇用于分割 tripton 和浮游植物的吸收。水样先通过直径为 47 mm、孔径为 0.70- μm 的 Whatman 玻璃纤维 GF/F 过滤器过滤, 然后再通过直径为 25 mm、孔径为 0.22- μm 的 Millipore 过滤器过滤, 测量 CDOM 吸收。使用 Shimadzu UV-2401PC 紫外-可见分光光度计测量其他三种组分的吸收系数; 详细的测量过程由 Zhang et al. [12] 描述。浮游植物吸收 Chla 浓度之比和 tripton 吸收与 tripton 浓度之比定义为浮游植物的比吸收系数 $a_{ph}(\lambda)$ 和 tripton $a_d(\lambda)$ 。

$$a_{ph}^*(\lambda) = a_{ph}(\lambda) / C_{Chla} \quad (5)$$

$$a_d^*(\lambda) = a_d(\lambda) / C_{Tripton} \quad (6)$$

其中 C_{Chla} 和 $C_{Tripton}$ 是 Chla 和 tripton 的浓度。

除纯水 $a_w(\lambda)$ 外的颗粒物质的光束衰减在一个 4 厘米径长的比色管中测量, 以 350 和 800 nm 之间的 Milli-Q 水为参考, 间隔 1 nm, 使用 Shimadzu UV-2401PC UV-Vis

分光光度计的标准探测器。所述的比色管被放置在离检测器相对较大的距离(5 厘米)处。光束衰减系数由以下公式得到[20]:

$$c_{t-w}(\lambda) = 2.303D(\lambda)/r \quad (7)$$

长为 λ 的光密度, r 是比色杯路径长度以米为单位。因子 2.303 用于将光密度值从基数

式中, $c_{t-w}(\lambda)$ 为波长 λ (m1) 下除纯水外的其他颗粒物质的束衰减系数, $D(\lambda)$ 为波长 λ 下的光密度, r 为比色管路径长度, 单位为米。用 2.303 因子将光密度值从以 10 为底的对数转换为自然对数尺度。

$c_{t-w}(\lambda)$ 表示为所有颗粒物与 CDOM 的吸收散射系数之和。由于 CDOM 没有散射, 粒子散射 $b_p(\lambda)$ 的光谱由以下方法获得:

$$b_p(\lambda) = c_{t-w}(\lambda) - a_p(\lambda) - a_{CDOM}(\lambda) \quad (8)$$

根据粒子的散射系数计算出粒子的后向散射系数 $bbp(\lambda)$ 。后向散射概率($\beta = bbp/bp$)与粒子分布和折射率有关。Sun et al.[21]根据 2006 年太湖 AC-S 和 HS-6 对 64 个点的吸收、光束衰减和散射系数的原位测量, 发现 β 在 440 nm 处范围为 0.010 ~ 0.028, 均值为 0.018 0.004。虽然一些研究表明 β 可以弱依赖于波长[22], [23]。然而, Whitmire 等人[24]发现, 在 440 620 nm 范围内, 5 个波长的光谱后向散射概率 β 没有显著的光谱依赖性。因此, 本文取 β 均值为 0.018, 在太湖[21]中观测到。然而, 稍后, 我们测试了这个假设对建模和检索精度的影响。

纯水的后向散射系数是散射系数的一半。纯水的散射系数采用如下公式[25]:

$$b_{bw}(\lambda) = 0.5b_w(\lambda) = 0.00144 \left(\frac{\lambda}{500} \right)^{-4.32} \quad (9)$$

总后向散射系数为颗粒与纯水后向散射系数之和:

$$b_{bt}(\lambda) = b_{bp}(\lambda) + b_{bw}(\lambda). \quad (10)$$

2.4 遥感反射率的建模

遥感反射在水面 $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0)$ 从辐照度计算反射率 $R(\lambda, 0)$, 后者除以所谓的几何因子

(Q),这是一个非波长依赖型的估计陆上升流辐射的比值($\lambda, 0$)下降辐照度 $E_d(\lambda, 0)$ 。

$$\begin{aligned} R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^-) &= L_u(\lambda, 0^-)/E_d(\lambda, 0^-) = \frac{E_u(\lambda, 0^-)}{Q \cdot E_d(\lambda, 0^-)} \\ &= \frac{R(\lambda, 0^-)}{Q} = \frac{f}{Q} \cdot \frac{b_{bt}(\lambda)}{a_t(\lambda) + b_{bt}(\lambda)}. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

(11)中的最后一项是所谓的戈登近似, 它将亚表面辐照反射率 $R(\lambda, 0)$ 与光学厚介质中的总吸收和散射联系起来。Austin[26]提出了 0.544 的系数来将地表以上的辐亮度与地表以下的辐亮度进行关联。因此, 水面上方的遥感反射率 $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^+)$ 可以计算如下:

$$R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^+) = 0.544R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^-) = 0.544 \frac{f}{Q} \cdot \frac{b_{bt}(\lambda)}{a_t(\lambda) + b_{bt}(\lambda)}. \quad (12)$$

蒙特卡罗研究[20]发现, f 主要是太阳仰角的函数, 可以很好地表示为 μ_0 的线性函数, μ_0 是光子与水面下垂直方向夹角的平均余弦:

$$f = 0.975 - 0.629\mu_0. \quad (13)$$

μ_0 的值取决于太阳高度和直接辐射与扩散辐射的比例。 μ_0 的值是根据采样时间、纬度和太阳高度角计算出来的。

(11)中的 Q 与 μ_0 呈负相关。理论上, Q 值在 0.3 - 6.5 之间, 但一般预期为 3 - 4[27]。本文采用经验方程 $Q = 2.38/\mu_0$ 计算 q [6]。冬、春、夏、秋季节 f/Q 均值分别为 0.158、0.153、0.152、0.157。

2.5 数据分析

Chla 浓度高的三个位点($>500 \mu g \cdot L^{-1}$)排除在本文数据集之外。统计分析(均值拟合、线性拟合和非线性拟合)采用 SPSS 11.0 Windows 统计软件包进行。回归的均方根误差(RMSE)和相对误差(RE)的计算方法如下:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_{Est,i} - x_{Obs,i})^2}{n}} \quad (14)$$

$$RE = \frac{(x_{Est} - x_{Obs})}{x_{Obs}} \times 100\% \quad (15)$$

其中, $x_{Est,i}$, $x_{Obs,i}$ 分别为估计值和实测值, n 为数据点个数。

3 结果与分析

3.1 光学活性物质的时空变化

三种旋光活性物质(TSM、Chla 和 CDOM)等指标在季节内和季节间的浓度变化较大(表 1), 反映了大浅水湖泊的时空异质性。

TSM 浓度在冬季显著高于其他 3 个季节(方差分析, $p < 0.001$)。相比之下, Chla 浓度在冬季显著低于其他三个季节(方差分析, $p < 0.001$), 对应于显著的藻华的消失和存在。虽然冬季没有出现明显的藻华, 但 Chla 浓度仍较高, 平均值为 $16.5 \pm 6.6 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, 表明太湖是一个高度富营养化湖泊。冬季的 TSM、tripton 和 aCDOM 平均值(440)分别为其他 3 个季节的 2.95、3.35 和 1.29 倍。而冬季 Chla 平均值是其他 3 个季节的 0.34 倍。

光学活性物质的浓度存在一定的空间差异。三种视活性物质在梅梁湾和湖北的浓度均高于湖南。Chla 和 CDOM 的平均浓度在样带 1、2 和 3 中显著高于样带 4(方差分析, $p < 0.001$)。在不同季节, 4 个样带间总生物量的平均浓度差异不显著。

在夏季和秋季, TSM 和 Chla 浓度在梅梁湾和北部湖区显著升高, 而梅梁湾和北部湖区则发生了严重的藻华。相比之下, 春季 Chla 浓度最高的地方是在湖的西南部, 39 和 40 点附近, 那里发生了强烈的藻华。

冬季全湖 Chla 浓度相对于其他三个季节处于较低水平。在冬季, 由于水下水生植被的变形和消失, 以及采样前明显的风浪作用引起的沉积物再悬浮, TSM 总体浓度较高。1 月 4 日、5 日和 6 日的平均风速分别为 7.2 、 5.6 和 $6.6 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ 。

冬季 CTSM 与 CChla 无相关性;而在其他 3 个季节, 两者均呈显著正相关($p < 0.001$)。说明在春、夏、秋三季, 由于频繁的藻华对 TSM 的贡献较大, TSM 与 Chla 之间的相互依赖性较强。TSM 含有有机粒子和无机粒子。对于发生藻华的水体, TSM 除无机物质外, 还含有大量的有机质。

		C_{TSM} $mg\ l^{-1}$	$C_{Tripton}$ $mg\ l^{-1}$	C_{Chla} $\mu g\ l^{-1}$	$a_{CDOM}(440)$ m^{-1}	Transpa rency cm	Depth m	T °C	V $m\ s^{-1}$
Winter (Jan.1-7)	Min	16.6	15.9	4.9	0.38	8	1.35	0.4	0.0
	Max	285.6	281.7	29.8	2.36	68	2.60	8.5	5.3
	Mean	130.2	128.2	16.5	0.98	17	2.04	3.7	2.57
	SD	57.8	57.7	6.6	0.33	9	0.34	2.2	1.45
Spring (Apr.25-27)	Min	15.9	14.4	4.9	0.35	10	1.60	17.1	0.00
	Max	213.9	129.0	448.9	1.52	60	2.80	23.0	5.90
	Mean	52.6	45.7	59.3	0.74	33	2.22	19.2	3.08
	SD	35.7	25.2	94.7	0.25	14	0.33	1.6	1.39
Summer (Jul.28-Aug.1)	Min	12.2	11.8	4.8	0.27	20	1.80	29.3	0.0
	Max	108.5	94.1	360.7	1.52	70	3.20	32.4	4.90
	Mean	48.4	43.2	50.6	0.71	34	2.47	31.1	3.12
	SD	23.2	19.4	58.1	0.26	12	0.36	1.0	0.97
Autumn (Oct.12-15)	Min	10.3	7.9	4.0	0.46	10	1.70	23.0	0.00
	Max	137.0	74.1	246.6	1.52	85	2.90	26.0	5.05
	Mean	31.3	26.0	35.7	0.84	38	2.37	24.3	2.63
	SD	21.0	12.8	46.9	0.20	12	0.30	0.8	1.15

T: water temperature; V: wind velocity; SD – standard deviation

表 1 季节性旋光活性物质与其他指标的比较

3.2 吸收系数的变化

tripton、浮游植物、CDOM 的光谱吸收系数和总吸收系数如图 2 所示。

CDOM 的吸收系数在 700 nm 附近接近零, 在 350 700 nm 范围内随波长的减小呈指数增长。在之前的研究中, 双曲拟合被认为是一种比线性拟合[12], [28]更好的方法。因此, 考虑到 CDOM 的吸收系数在大于 600 nm 的波长范围内几乎为零或为负, 本文采用双曲线拟合方法拟合波长为 300 600 nm 的 CDOM 光谱。基于 197 个数据点(4 季 50 个站点 3 个高 Chla 点), CDOM 吸收光谱斜率(S)的均值和标准差分别为 6.36 和 0.83 nm^{-1} 。这些值与冬季和夏季[12]值非常接近。因此, CDOM 的吸收可以用如下公式:

$$a_{CDOM}(\lambda) = a_{CDOM}(440)(\lambda/440)^{-6.36} \quad (16)$$

在四季中, tripton 的吸收系数随波长的增加而减小(图 2)。许多研究表明, tripton 具有相对稳定的吸收特性, 可以用指数函数[29], [30]来描述。考虑到 CDOM 和 tripton 的吸收光谱形状非常相似, 本文对其吸收光谱进行了双曲拟合。基于 2004 年 7 月至 2007 年 4 月太湖不同区域 727 个样本的大数据集, 发现双曲线模型比简单指数模型(未发表数据)更准确地反映了太湖的 tripton 吸收。本文采用双曲线拟合, 在 400 ~ 700 nm 波长范围内, tripton 的光谱斜率值(Sd)范围较窄, 为 4.96 ~ 7.50 nm^{-1} , 均值为 6.27 nm^{-1} , 变异系数为 6.1%。CDOM 光谱斜率均值(6.36 nm^{-1})与 tripton 光谱斜率均值

(6.27 nm^{-1})非常接近。对于四季, tripton 的吸收可以表示为:

$$a_d(\lambda) = a_d(440)(\lambda/440)^{-6.27}. \quad (17)$$

浮游植物的吸收光谱显示, 色素有两个诊断吸收峰, 分别在蓝色波长(约 440 nm)和红色波长(约 675 nm)(图 2)。由于色素浓度的显著差异, 浮游植物的吸收系数在空间和时间上存在显著差异。在春、夏、秋三季的藻华期间, 浮游植物的吸收在某些地点非常高。

总吸收光谱非常类似于非生物性浮游物,减少 400 至 600 海里,除了几个网站,有严重的赤潮在水面上(图 2),表明强烈的吸收通过非生物性浮游物浅湖以其高胰化蛋白脲浓度(7.9 - 281.7 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)。非生物性浮游物的平均吸收,和 CDOM 也表明,总吸收光谱以 tripton 为主[图 3(a)]。本文浮游植物的特异性吸收光谱在[29], [31]范围内,但由于太湖 Chla 浓度较高,相对于清澈的海洋水体而言,其值较低[图 3(b)]。浮游植物的比吸收系数随着 Chla 浓度的增加有降低的趋势,这是由于所谓的包装效应。 $a_d(443)$ 的平均值为 $0.057 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, 高于 Babin et al.[31]的平均值 $0.041 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ 。造成这种差异的部分原因是计算方法的不同。我们注意到, Babin et al.[31]利用 TSM 浓度(包括浮游植物)计算了 tripton 的比吸收系数。然而,我们通过排除浮游植物来计算特里顿浓度。在富营养化的太湖,夏季藻华期间浮游植物是 TSM 的重要组成部分,这种效应在太湖最为显著。此外,沿海和湖泊水体的来源和矿物组成的差异也可能导致 $a(443)$ 的差异。

图2 非生物性浮游物、浮游植物和 CDOM 的吸收光谱和总吸收系数

3.3 遥感反射率的建模

每个站的水上遥感反射率按(12)和式(13)建模。总吸收和后向散射由(4)、(8)、(9)和(10)测量的固有光学性质和应用获得。

遥感反射率的季节变化如图4所示。这三种光学活性物质的浓度及其固有光学性质的大变异性导致模拟的遥感反射光谱的幅度有很大的空间和时间变异性。反射光谱在不同的地点和季节变化很大。为了验证模型 $Rrs(\lambda, 0+)$ ，图5显示了2006年7月两个典型站点实测 $Rrs(\lambda, 0+)$ 与模型 $Rrs(\lambda, 0+)$ 的比较。实测 Rrs 和模型 $Rrs(\lambda, 0+)$ 吻合较好，说明在实验室中通过测量波束衰减系数和吸收系数来模拟遥感反射率是合理可行的。然而，在较短的波长(小于 550 nm)下，模型的 $Rrs(\lambda, 0+)$ 普遍低于实测值;这一误差归因于散射系数和后向散射系数的不确定性。散射系数由分光光度计(8)测量的光束衰减和吸收系数计算而来，由于分光光度计的接收角为 5° ，因此会损失一些后向散射辐射。由于后向散射系数随波长的减小而增大，因此在波长较短时，后向散射系数的损失项更大，导致模型 $Rrs(\lambda, 0+)$ 普遍低于实测值。测量的 $Rrs(\lambda, 0+)$ 和模拟的 $Rrs(\lambda, 0+)$ 的差异也可能来自于观测 $Rrs(\lambda, 0+)$ 的误差。虽然水在大

多数情况下是平静的，由于天窗反射的潜在误差仍然存在。此外，空气-水界面的反射率对风浪的影响不大，本文将其设为常数，从而产生了潜在误差。

这些模拟的光谱在量级、形状和光谱特征上与在太湖[14]测得的典型反射光谱非常接近。遥感反射率与光谱后向散射与所有光学活性物质光谱吸收和后向散射之和的比值成正比(12)。光谱反射峰和局部最小值一般与总吸收光谱呈负相关。总的来说，反射峰出现在 560、650 和 700 nm 附近(图 4 和图 5)。反射最小值出现在近 400 nm 附近，这是由于颗粒和溶解物质的强烈吸收(图 2)和近 800 nm 附近，这是由于纯水的吸收。由于模拟的反射光谱是根据实测的吸收系数和后向散射系数计算出来的，因此消除了底部反射率对总反射率的影响。然而，海底反射率可能会影响实地测量的反射率，特别是在典型的大型植物优势区(徐口湾和东湖太湖)[11]。如既往研究[13]、[32]基于原位和遥测的 $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^+)$ 得到了两个海湾(徐口湾和东湖太湖)Chla 浓度和水质的显著误差。

在浑浊的太湖中，400 ~ 500 nm 范围内，溶解性有机物和 triton 的吸收和颗粒物的散射对反射率的贡献最大，该范围内反射率光谱的一个共同特征是对 Chla 浓度变化的敏感性较低。蓝绿比 $R_{rs}(440)/R_{rs}(550)$ 不能用于估算研究水域中的 chla。因此，短波长 $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^+)$ 测量值和模型值的差异对太湖 CChla 的估算没有影响。绿色区域在 550 570 nm 附近有一个峰(图 4 和 5)，这是由于所有藻类色素的吸收极小(图 2)，ISM 和浮游植物细胞的散射控制了这一区域的反射率大小。在 675 nm 附近，反射率最小是由浮游植物吸收的结果，特别是在色素浓度高的区域。然而，除太湖 Chla 浓度外，该区域的反射率还受到 triton 浓度的强烈影响，降低了 $R_{rs}(675)$ 与 Chla 的相关性。局部最小值在 625 nm 左右是由于藻蓝蛋白的吸收。这种色素主要存在于蓝藻中，因此，625 nm 的局部反射最小值经常被用于监测富营养化湖泊[8]，[9]中的蓝藻华。

在 700 nm 附近有一个明显的峰，对应于颗粒散射的减小和纯水吸收的增加。随着 Chla 浓度的增加，这个峰的位置向更长的波长移动。从图 6 可以看出峰的位置与 CChla 密切相关。这说明，除 Chla 吸收外，tripton 散射对该光谱区域的反射率起着重要的控制作用。在其他生产性浑浊水体[33]、[34]中，随着 Chla 浓度的增加，700 nm 附近的反射率峰位置发生红移。

我们在太湖进行了不同季节、不同太阳天顶角(15 ~ 77)下水体生物光学特性的测量。然而,估计的 f/Q 值的标准差小于 2.5%, 平均 f/Q 值为 0.1553, 与 Case-1 waters[35] 报告的值非常接近。虽然 f 和 Q 在很大程度上取决于太阳天顶角和水的固有光学性质, 但 f/Q 基本上与太阳天顶角无关。这些结果表明, 从我们在这些 Case-2 水域中测量的几何最低点来看, 观测到的 f/Q 数量的变化不是非常大, 与 Case-1 水域没有明显区别。

图4 不同季节的遥感反射率

图5 2006年7月两个站点在水面 $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^+)$ 上方的实测和模拟遥感反射率的比较

图 6 700 nm 附近遥感反射峰位置与 Ch1a 浓度的关系

3.4 叶绿素 a 检索模型

准确掌握太湖 Ch1a 浓度和藻华的时空变化信息，对于监测太湖水质、了解太湖水体富营养化的机理、发布水质预警、保护太湖周边饮用水厂具有重要意义。然而，目前运行的卫星 Ch1a 算法，如 MERIS，在极其浑浊的太湖水域中应用，往往会导致反演错误。

在以往的太湖研究中，CCh1a[13]、[14]的估计主要采用单波段、波段比和一阶导数方法。相比之下，本文采用三波段反射率模型来估算高浊度和高生物量条件下的 ch1a。该模型在所有季节的准确性和执行能力上进行了测试。

最近，提出了一个概念模型，该模型包含光谱的红色和近红外(NIR)范围内三个光谱波段的遥感反射率，用于反演浑浊产水[33]，[34]中的 Ch1a [36]。

$$\text{Ch1a} = A \times [R_{rs}^{-1}(\lambda_1) - R_{rs}^{-1}(\lambda_2)] \times R_{rs}(\lambda_3) + B \quad (18)$$

其中 A 和 B 是常数，依赖于特定的固有光学性质，三个波长必须先验或后验确定。

三波段反射率模型最初是为估算陆地植被色素含量而开发的。第一波段 λ_1 反射率对 CCh1a 最敏感。Rrs(λ_1)还受 tripton、CDOM 和水的吸收以及所有颗粒物质的后向散射的影响。后向散射和被 tripton 和 CDOM 吸收的影响可以通过第二个光谱波段来最小化，其中 Rrs(λ_2)对浮游植物、tripton 和 CDOM 的吸收最不敏感。Rrs(λ_3)受浮游植物、tripton 和 CDOM 的影响最小，第三波段的总吸收是对水吸收的测量。基于

这些假设,三个波段的光谱范围分别被限制在 660 690、700 750 和 730 750 nm。我们参考 Dall Olmo 和 Gitelson[36]和 Gitelson et al.[34]对这种带的选择进行了详细的描述和解释。一些研究表明,三光谱波段反射模型 $[r_{rs}(\lambda_1) r_{rs}(\lambda_2)] R_{rs}(\lambda_3)$ 比带比法更精确。

为了找到最好的三个乐队,估计 Chla 浓度在太湖湖三波长 λ_1 的组合从 660 年到 690 海里, λ_2 从 700 年到 750 海里, λ_3 从 730 年到 750 海里使用遥感反射率与 CChla 用于相关性建模。本文采用均方根误差(RMSE)判断最佳波段组合。线性相关表明,三波段反射模型 $[R_{rs}(690) R_{rs}(703)] R_{rs}(759)$ 的 RMSE 最低,相关系数最高($r^2 = 0.94$),估计精度最高。得到的 Chla 估计模型以及实测和估计的 Chla 的比较如图 7 所示。RMSE 和 RE 分别为 $15.1 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (与平均 CChla 的比值为 37.3%)和 44.4%。虽然 $[R_{rs}(690) R_{rs}(703)] R_{rs}(759)$ 给出了最小的 RMSE,但相应的 RE 略大于最小的 42.5%。三波段反射率模型 $[R_{rs}(690) R_{rs}(703)] R_{rs}(759)$ 可用于太湖富营养化浑浊水体的测量。

由(11)和(12)可以得出,模型遥感反射率的误差源是由 f/Q 和后向散射概率(β)导出的。然而,在三波段模型中, f/Q 与波长无关,在模型中被剔除,因此对 CChla 的检索精度没有影响。本文采用 0.012、0.015、0.021 和 0.024(33%的标准差相对于 0.018)来检验三波段模型对 β 的 Chla 检索精度的灵敏度。表 II 显示了使用不同 β 值的 CChla 估计的拟合方程、 r^2 、RMSE 和 RE。 β 的变化对 CChla 精度的 RMSE 和 RE 影响较小。以 0.012 为 β 值的模型与以 0.018 为 β 值的模型相比, RMSE 和 RE 的最大偏差分别为 1.9%和 2.1%。此外,不同的 β 值只会改变检索模型的线性斜率,而不会改变检索模型的截距。结果表明,本文建立的三波段模型对不确定性参数不敏感,可用于 CChla 估计。

此外,图 8 显示了测量和建模的对比 $[r_{rs}(690) r_{rs}(703)] R_{rs}(759)$,以进一步验证使用所建模的遥感反射率的三波段模型。测量和建模 $[r_{rs}(690) r_{rs}(703)] R_{rs}(759)$ 由一个非常重要的线性关系($r^2 = 0.90$),斜率接近 1.0(0.935)(图 8)。这种分析进一步表明,建模 $R_{rs}(\lambda_0 +)$ 可以用来估计 CChla 基于 threeband 模型与测量 $R_{rs}(\lambda_0 +)$ 谱。

为了比较三波段反射率模型与其他方法的精度,还采用了带比法估计了 CChla。

为了找到波段比法的最佳波段，使用 350 ~ 800 nm 任意两个波长的波段比与 CChla 进行相关性。线性相关性表明 R_{rs} 的比率(713 年)/ $R_{rs}(674)$ 给最高的决定系数($r^2 = 0.92$) 和 RMSE 最低($18.0 \mu g \cdot L^{-1}$)(图 9)。三波段反射率模型[$R_{rs}(690) - R_{rs}(703)$]/ $R_{rs}(759)$ 比波段比值的方法更精确的 $R_{rs}(713) / R_{rs}(674)$ 一直在验证其他案例 2 水[33],[34]。三级模型与光谱波段优化内陆水域, Chla 从 4.4 到 $217.3 \mu g \cdot L^{-1}$ [36]和从 107 年到 3078 $\mu g \cdot L^{-1}$ [33], 允许精确估计 Chla 应用于太湖湖时, 尽管这个湖有一个非常不同的光学活性物质的合成(Chla、胰化蛋白胨和 CDOM)。

图 7 利用三波段反射率模型反演 Chla 浓度模型及实测值与估测值的比较

图 8 测量和建模的比较 ($R_{rs}^{-1}(690) - R_{rs}^{-1}(703)$) $\times R_{rs}(759)$)

图 9 利用带比法反演 Chla 浓度模型及实测值与估测值的比较

β	Retrieval equation*	r^2	RMSE ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$)	RE (%)
0.012	$C_{\text{Chla}}=322.3x+27.6$	0.94	15.4	45.1
0.015	$C_{\text{Chla}}=335.1x+27.6$	0.94	15.2	44.5
0.018	$C_{\text{Chla}}=347.7x+27.6$	0.94	15.1	44.2
0.021	$C_{\text{Chla}}=360.2x+27.6$	0.94	15.0	44.1
0.024	$C_{\text{Chla}}=372.4x+27.6$	0.94	15.0	44.1

*: Here x is $[R_{rs}^{-1}(690)-R_{rs}^{-1}(703)] \times R_{rs}(759)$

表 2 五种不同后向散射概率值的三波段模型反演方程及精度比较

3.5 检索模型验证

为了进一步理解三波段模型的适用性，我们提出了三波段模型的性能评估使用一个独立的数据集，包括两个调查。CChla 范围为 1.6 ~ 202.0 $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ ，平均值为 29.6 $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ ，符合模型建立时的 CChla 范围。三波段模型和带比模型测得和估计的 CChla 比较如图 10 所示。三波段测得和估计的 CChla 符合良好的线性关系($r^2 = 0.92$ ，斜率 0.967 接近 1.0)。验证数据集的 RMSE 和 RMSE 占平均 CChla 的百分比低于校准数据集的 RMSE(图 7 和图 10)，说明可以接受三波段模型的性能。与三波段模型相比，带比方法的 RMSE 和 RE 分别为三波段模型的 1.45 倍和 2.01 倍。与带比方法相比，三带模型性能更好的原因之一是，三带模型通过 $R_{rs}(\lambda 2)$ 和 $R_{rs}(\lambda 3)$ 完全消除了后向散射的干扰。

选取的3个波段基本都在MERIS通道范围内(通道8、9和10分别为681/8、709/10和754/8 nm),这使得利用MERIS图像准确估计Chla成为可能。利用MERIS影像[R_{rs}(681) R_{rs}(709)] R_{rs}(754)中心波段,确定系数、均方根误差(RMSE)和平均RE分别为0.92、17.0 μg·L⁻¹和48.1%,具有较高的反演精度。

虽然本文算法是针对MERIS等星载仪器的典型波段设置而推导出来的,但在实际的MERIS或MODIS太湖影像中研究其适用性仍具有相当大的挑战性。一个主要的关注来源是算法的鲁棒性不完善的大气校正浑浊水域[37],[38]。在近红外波长下,气溶胶载荷和埃系数的微小误差通常会在较短波长[39]下转化为归一化的离水辐亮度的显著偏差。目前,在Case-1水体中广泛使用的用于大气校正的黑像元假设不适用于含沙量或Chla浓度较高的Case-2生产性水体。然而,一旦在极其浑浊水域上的大气校正程序得到改进,三波段算法可能会是一种相当棒的Chla检索算法,因为R_{rs}(λ)中的偏移,在大气校正程序中的误差,部分抵消了在较窄的波长间隔(681 754 nm)的R_{rs}比s。

图 10 测量和建模的比较

4 总结

在太湖等浑浊富营养化水体中，Chla 的有效遥感反演是一个重大挑战。尽管之前的几项研究已经在 Case-1 水域提供了可靠的 Chla 检测，但许多研究未能完全支持在光学复杂的 Case-2 水域中准确识别、监测和预测未来的藻华位置。太湖 Chla 的反演精度在很大程度上取决于应用遥感生物光学算法开发、验证和改进中使用的原位数据的准确性和一致性。本文利用 4 个不同季节的生物光学测量数据，对 3 种光学活性物质浓度和固有光学性质的时空变异性进行了模拟。我们发现，在红色和近红外波段，三波段模型[r1 rs(690) r1 rs(703)] Rrs(759)， CDOM 和 tripton 吸收对反射率的影响最小，可以比以往广泛使用的波段比方法更好地反演 Chla。提出的三波段算法的波长符合 MERIS 波段和为从 MERIS 卫星监测 Case-2 水域的浮游植物暴发提供了良好的基础。值得注意的是，利用 MERIS 中心带[r1 rs(681) r1 rs(709)] Rrs(754)] 的三波段模型也可以准确估计四季 Chla 在 $4.0 \sim 448.9 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ 范围内的变化，这表明 MERIS 图像不仅可以用于监测低至中等 Chla 浓度的水体(正如之前的研究中所做的那样)，也可以用于监测极度浑浊和富营养化的水体。然而，该算法能否成功应用于卫星数据，在很大程度上取决于湖泊上空近红外区域大气校正的精度。这可能会给未来任务中的近红外波段定位和描述陆地对太湖等相对较小湖泊大气校正的影响带来新的挑战。

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附录 B 外文原文

Modeling Remote-Sensing Reflectance and Retrieving Chlorophyll-a Concentration in Extremely Turbid Case-2 Waters (Lake Taihu, China)

Yunlin Zhang, Mingliang Liu, Boqiang Qin, Hendrik Jan van der Woerd, Junsheng Li, and Yunliang Li

Abstract

Accurate assessment of concentration of chlorophyll a (Chla) and correct identification of algal blooms by remote sensing have previously been a great challenge in the optically complex Case-2 waters. In this paper, we used a large biooptical data set to model the remote-sensing reflectance in an extremely turbid and biologically productive Lake Taihu in China. The conceptual three-band model $[R_{rs-1}(\lambda_1) - R_{rs-1}(\lambda_2)] \times R_{rs}(\lambda_3)$ (where R_{rs} represents remote-sensing reflectance just above the water surface) to retrieve Chla concentration was calibrated and validated, and a detailed assessment of its accuracy was obtained. Water samples were collected for four seasons from 2006 to 2007 at 50 sites, covering different ecosystem types, and contained three very variable optically active substances (tripton 7.9–281.7 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, Chla 4.0–448.9 $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, and chromophoric dissolved organic matter [aCDOM(440)] 0.27–2.36 m^{-1}). Secchi disk transparency ranged from 8 to 85 cm. The retrieval accuracies (r^2) of the optimal three-band model and the related band-ratio method were 0.94 and 0.92, while the root mean-square errors (RMSE) and relative errors (RE) were 15.1 $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ (37.3% accounting for the mean value) and 18.0 $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, and 44.4% and 60.2%, respectively. Applications of the three-band model

using MERIS central bands $[Rrs-1(681) - Rrs-1(709)] \times Rrs(754)$ also allowed accurate estimation of Chla, with r^2 , RMSE, and RE of 0.92, $17.0 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, and 48.1%, respectively. The establishment of a simple and robust biooptical model with high retrieval accuracy and known error budgets will help the rapid, accurate, and real-time assessment of algal blooms using in situ and satellite remote-sensing techniques.

Index Terms—Absorption coefficient, chlorophyll a (Chla), error budgets, Lake Taihu, remote-sensing reflectance.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last few 20 years, increased nutrient loadings, driven by industrial development, human-population growth, and changes in land use, have resulted in eutrophication and increased phytoplankton concentrations in Lake Taihu in China [1]. In recent summers, the accumulation of surface blooms of the cyanobacteria *Microcystis* spp. has impeded normal operation of drinking-water plants for the large cities of Wuxi and Wujing, and from May to October, particularly high cyanobacterial concentrations have been recorded in Meiliang Bay and Zhushan Bay within the lake. In particular, in early June in 2007, a cyanobacterial bloom in Gonghu Bay polluted the biggest drinking-water plant in Wuxi City, interrupting water supply in Wuxi City for several days. Furthermore, the cyanobacterial blooms in Lake Taihu pose additional potential health risks, due to the toxic *Microcystis* spp., particularly in summer [2]. Exposure to toxic *Microcystis* spp. could lead to liver failure in wild animals, livestock, and aquatic life, as well as human illnesses and mortality. Some reports suggest that the incidence of human primary liver cancer in the eastern region of China is related to the presence of microcystins found in drinking water [3], [4].

Conventional chlorophyll-a (Chla) monitoring programs are limited in their effectiveness in Lake Taihu, because they only provide spatial distribution data of Chla concentration along their routes during fixed cruises. The restricted temporal and spatial aspects of such conventional ship-based water-sampling programs are not adequate to report changes in phytoplankton biomass. This is particularly problematic during bloom

conditions when the variability in phytoplankton density is particularly high, with accumulations happening in time periods as brief as several hours or within a single day, and when there is frequent disturbance due to wind waves. The serious 2007 contamination of the water supply to Wuxi City was not detected because the algal-bloom accumulation and deposition were not recognized due to the low frequency and small area of conventional sampling.

In order to mitigate the impacts of algal blooms and issue warnings to drinking-water plants in Lake Taihu, it is therefore essential to detect, monitor, and forecast the development and movement of blooms using more detailed and effective techniques. In some coastal and lake waters, the use of airborne and satellite remote sensing has demonstrated to provide more reliable temporal–spatial information about water quality and the extent of the cyanobacterial blooms than does conventional monitoring [5]–[9]. Thus, this approach was adopted for Lake Taihu.

Lake Taihu is a large eutrophic shallow lake with high spatial heterogeneity; different ecosystem types (algal-dominated, macrophyte-dominated, and transition regions); complicated dynamics of phytoplankton, particulate matter, and chromophoric dissolved organic matter (CDOM); and variable biooptical properties [10]–[12]. Remote sensing is a potentially powerful tool for studying phytoplankton dynamics and managing water quality in the Lake Taihu by virtue of its ability to resolve steep spatial gradients and temporal variability in optically significant constituents. However, despite this potential, such an approach has not been widely used, and the temporal–spatial variations of biooptical properties and the concentrations of three optically active substances (tripton, phytoplankton, and CDOM) in Lake Taihu remain poorly characterized. As a result, most studies have focused on the collection of data for optically active substances based on the in situ measurement of the remote-sensing reflectance [13], [14]. To address this need, the aims of this paper are as follows: 1) compare the variations of the concentrations and spectral absorption coefficients of three optically active substances for four different

seasons; 2) model the remote-sensing reflectance and discuss its spectral characteristics; 3) optimize a three-band model to estimate Chla concentration; and 4) characterize the error budget of the retrieval model.

Fig. 1. Distribution of transects and sampling sites.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Site and Sampling Schedule

Optical measurements were made and water samples were taken at 50 sites in different regions of the lake: transect 1 (sites 1–16) followed a semicircular route around Meiliang Bay in the north, transect 2 (sites 17–29) originated in Gonghu Bay and extended southwest across the lake center, transect 3 (sites 30–40) originated in Guanghu Bay and extended southwest across the lake center, and transect 4 (sites 41–50) originated in Xukou Bay and extended southwest across the lake, passing south of Xishan Island (Fig. 1). Measurements and water samples were taken on four seasonal cruises: winter (January 7–9, 2006), spring (April 25–27, 2007), summer (July 28–August 1, 2006), and autumn (October 12–15, 2006).

In order to validate the three-band model and band-ratio method used to estimate Chla

concentration, an independent data set ($32 \times 2 = 64$ samplings) was obtained from two sampling cruises in May (17–19) and October (16–18) in 2005. The sample sites in these investigations were basically evenly distributed over the Lake Taihu [15].

B. Sample Preparation

Samples for Chla were filtered on Whatman GF/C fiberglass filters. The Chla and phaeophytin a (Pa) were extracted with ethanol (90%) at 80 °C and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 750 and 665 nm with correction for Pa.

To obtain total suspended matter (TSM), water samples were filtered through precombusted Whatman GF/C fiberglass filters (450 °C for 4 h) to remove suspended organic matter, dried (105 °C for 4 h), and weighed. The filters were recombusted at 450 °C for 4 h and weighed again to obtain inorganic suspended matter (ISM). By subtracting ISM from TSM, organic suspended matter was obtained.

In order to separate the dry weight of tripton from the dry weight of total particles, the dominant species of *Microcystis* and *Scenedesmus* in Lake Taihu were cultured in the laboratory to measure dry weight, Chla, and Pa concentrations in different growth periods. Surface algal-bloom samples were collected during calm-weather conditions and cleared using distilled water to obtain the relative pure phytoplankton (excluding tripton). Then, the sample was put under dark condition. Every three days, the sample was collected to measure the dry weight, Chla, and Pa concentrations. We found that a simple linear equation could describe the relation between the dry weight of phytoplankton and the sum of Chla and Pa concentrations

$$C_{\text{phytoplankton}} = 0.09C_{\text{Chla+Pa}} (r^2 = 0.98, n=31, p < 0.001) \quad (1)$$

where $C_{\text{phytoplankton}}$ is the dry weight of phytoplankton and $C_{\text{Chla+Pa}}$ is the sum of Chla and Pa concentrations. The concentration of tripton (C_{Tripton}) is obtained as the difference of TSM (C_{TSM}) and phytoplankton dry weight ($C_{\text{phytoplankton}}$).

C. Measurement of Remote-Sensing Reflectance and Inherent Optical Properties

Downwelling radiance and upwelling total radiance measurements were made by

using an ASD field spectrometer (Analytical Devices, Inc., Boulder, CO) with a spectral response range of 350–1000 nm and a spectral resolution of 3 nm. The “above-water method” was used to measure water-surface spectra [16]. An optical fiber was positioned at nadir on a mount extending away from the boat to reduce the influence of reflectance off of the vessel on collected spectra. The radiance spectra from the reference panel, water, and sky were measured at a height of approximately 0.3 m above the water surface under clear-sky conditions. At each sampling site, the relevant spectra were measured ten times to optimize the signal-to-noise ratio and, thus, reduce the error of in situ measurements. Each spectrum was sampled 90° azimuthally from the Sun and at a nadir viewing angle of 40°. The water-leaving radiance $L_w(\lambda, 0+)$ can be derived from the following:

$$L_w(\lambda, 0+) = L_{sw}(\lambda, 0+) - r_{sky} \cdot L_{sky}(\lambda) \quad (2)$$

where $L_{sw}(\lambda, 0+)$ is the upwelling radiance from the water and $L_{sky}(\lambda)$ is the sky radiance measured at the same azimuth angle and at 40° zenith angle. The r_{sky} is the specular reflectance of skylight at the air–water interface ranging from 0.022 for calm weather to 0.025 for a wind speed of up to 5 m · s⁻¹ [16]. A constant value of 0.0245 was used in this paper.

The incident downwelling irradiance $E_d(\lambda, 0+)$ was determined by measuring the radiance of the Lambertian reference panel $L_p(\lambda, 0+)$ as follows:

$$E_d(\lambda, 0+) = \pi L_p(\lambda, 0+) / \rho_p(\lambda) \quad (3)$$

where $\rho_p(\lambda)$ is the reflectance of the reference panel that has been accurately calibrated to 30%.

The remote-sensing reflectance above the water surface $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0+)$ is calculated as the ratio of water-leaving upwelling radiance $L_w(\lambda, 0+)$ to incident downwelling irradiance $E_d(\lambda, 0+)$. Some $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0+)$ spectra were excluded from the data set at sites with a thick algal bloom or macrophytes. A set of 176 $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0+)$ spectra was obtained in this paper.

The total absorption coefficient is the sum of the coefficients of tripton [$a_d(\lambda)$], phytoplankton [$a_{ph}(\lambda)$], CDOM

[aCDOM(λ)], and pure water

$$[a_w(\lambda)] a(\lambda) = a_d(\lambda) + a_{ph}(\lambda) + a_{CDOM}(\lambda) + a_w(\lambda). \quad (4)$$

The absorption coefficient of pure water $a_w(\lambda)$ reported by Smith and Baker [17] was used here. The coefficients $a_p(\lambda)$ (the absorption coefficient of total particulate matter including tripton and phytoplankton), $a_d(\lambda)$, and $a_{ph}(\lambda)$ were determined by the quantitative filter technique [18], where methanol was used to partition the absorption of tripton and phytoplankton. Water samples were first filtered through a 47-mm-diameter Whatman fiberglass GF/F filter with 0.70- μm pores and, then, refiltered through a 25-mm-diameter Millipore filter with 0.22- μm pores to measure CDOM absorption. The measurement of the absorption coefficients of the three other components was undertaken using a Shimadzu UV-2401PC UV-Vis spectrophotometer; the detailed measurement process has been described by Zhang et al. [12]. The ratios of phytoplankton absorption to Chla concentration and tripton absorption to tripton concentration are defined as the specific absorption coefficients of phytoplankton $a_{ph}^*(\lambda)$ and tripton $a_d^*(\lambda)$

$$a_{ph}^*(\lambda) = a_{ph}(\lambda)/C_{Chla} \quad (5)$$

$$a_d^*(\lambda) = a_d(\lambda)/C_{Tripton} \quad (6)$$

where C_{Chla} and $C_{Tripton}$ are Chla and tripton concentrations.

Beam attenuation of particulate matter except for pure water $ct-w(\lambda)$ was measured in a 4-cm path length cuvette against a reference of Milli-Q water between 350 and 800 nm at 1-nm intervals by a standard detector using a Shimadzu UV-2401PC UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The cuvette was positioned at a relatively large distance (5 cm) from the detector as described by Simis et al. [19]. The beam-attenuation coefficient was obtained based on the following [20]:

$$ct-w(\lambda) = 2.303D(\lambda)/r \quad (7)$$

matter except for pure water at wavelength where $ct-w(\lambda)$ is beam-attenuation coefficient of particulate $\lambda(m-1)$, $D(\lambda)$ is the optical density at wavelength λ , and r is the cuvette path length in meters. The factor of 2.303 was used to convert optical density values from a base

10 log to a natural log scale. $c_{t-w}(\lambda)$ was expressed as the sum of the absorption and scattering coefficients of all particulate matter and CDOM. Because CDOM has no scattering, spectra of particle scattering $b_p(\lambda)$ were obtained using the following:

$$b_p(\lambda) = c_{t-w}(\lambda) - a_p(\lambda) - a_{CDOM}(\lambda). \quad (8)$$

The backscattering coefficient ($b_{bp}(\lambda)$) of the particles is calculated from the scattering coefficient of particles. The backscattering probability ($\beta = b_{bp}/b_p$) is dependent on the distribution of particles and on the refractive index. Sun et al. [21] found β ranged from 0.010 to 0.028 with a mean value of 0.018 ± 0.004 at 440 nm based on in situ measurement of absorption, beam attenuation, and scattering coefficients of 64 sites using AC-S and HS-6 in Lake Taihu in 2006. Although some studies showed that β can be weakly dependent on wavelength [22], [23]. However, Whitmire et al. [24] found that there was no significant spectral dependence of the spectral backscattering probability β for each of five wavelengths in the range of 440–620 nm. Therefore, this paper took a mean β value of 0.018, as observed in Lake Taihu [21]. However, later on, we tested the impact of this assumption on the modeling and retrieval accuracy (in Section III-D).

The backscattering coefficient of pure water is half of the scattering coefficient. The scattering coefficient of pure water is adopted as follows [25]:

$$b_{bw}(\lambda) = 0.5b_w(\lambda) = 0.00144 \left(\frac{\lambda}{500} \right)^{-4.32}. \quad (9)$$

The total backscattering coefficient was the sum of the backscattering coefficients of particles and pure water

$$b_{bt}(\lambda) = b_{bp}(\lambda) + b_{bw}(\lambda). \quad (10)$$

D. Modeling of Remote-Sensing Reflectance

The remote-sensing reflectance just beneath the water surface $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^-)$ is calculated from irradiance reflectance $R(\lambda, 0^-)$, by dividing the latter by the so-called geometrical factor (Q), which is a wavelength-independent estimate of the ratio of the upwelling radiance $L_u(\lambda, 0^-)$ to the downwelling irradiance $E_d(\lambda, 0^-)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^-) &= L_u(\lambda, 0^-)/E_d(\lambda, 0^-) = \frac{E_u(\lambda, 0^-)}{Q \cdot E_d(\lambda, 0^-)} \\
 &= \frac{R(\lambda, 0^-)}{Q} = \frac{f}{Q} \cdot \frac{b_{bt}(\lambda)}{a_t(\lambda) + b_{bt}(\lambda)}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

The last term in (11) is the so-called Gordon approximation that relates the subsurface irradiance reflectance $R(\lambda, 0^-)$ to total absorption and scattering in an optically thick medium. Austin [26] proposed the factor of 0.544 for correlating radiance just above the surface to radiance just beneath the surface. Thus, remote-sensing reflectance just above the water surface $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^+)$ can be calculated as follows:

$$R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^+) = 0.544 \overline{R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^-)} = 0.544 f \cdot \frac{b_{bt}(\lambda)}{a_t(\lambda) + b_{bt}(\lambda)} \tag{12}$$

Monte Carlo studies [20] have found that f is mainly a function of solar-elevation angle that was reasonably well expressed as a linear function of μ_0 , the mean cosine of the angles the photons make with the vertical just beneath the water surface

$$f = 0.975 - 0.629\mu_0. \tag{13}$$

The value of μ_0 is dependent upon the solar elevation and the proportion of direct and diffuse radiations. The value of μ_0 is calculated according to the sampling time, latitude, and solar altitude angle.

Q in (11) was inversely related to μ_0 . In theory, Q ranges from 0.3 to 6.5 but is generally expected to be 3–4 [27]. Here, an empirical equation of $Q = 2.38/\mu_0$ was used to calculate Q [6]. The mean values of f/Q in winter, spring, summer, and autumn were 0.158, 0.153, 0.152, and 0.157, respectively.

E. Data Analysis

Statistical analyses (mean value, linear and nonlinear fitting) were performed with the statistical package SPSS 11.0 for Windows. The root mean-square error (RMSE) and relative error (RE) of regression are calculated by the following:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_{Est,i} - x_{Obs,i})^2}{n}} \tag{14}$$

$$RE = \frac{(x_{Est} - x_{Obs})}{x} \times 100\% \tag{15}$$

where $x_{Est,i}$ and $x_{Obs,i}$ are the estimated and measured values, respectively, and n is the number of data points.

TABLE I
SEASONAL COMPARISON OF OPTICALLY ACTIVE SUBSTANCES AND OTHER INDEXES

		C_{TSM} mg l ⁻¹	$C_{Trypton}$ mg l ⁻¹	C_{Chla} μg l ⁻¹	$a_{CDOM}(400)$ m ⁻¹	Transpa rency cm	Depth m	T °C	V m s ⁻¹
Winter (Jan.1-7)	Min	16.6	15.9	4.9	0.38	8	1.35	0.4	0.0
	Max	285.6	281.7	29.8	2.36	68	2.60	8.5	5.3
	Mean	130.2	128.2	16.5	0.98	17	2.04	3.7	2.57
	SD	57.8	57.7	6.6	0.33	9	0.34	2.2	1.45
Spring (Apr.25-27)	Min	15.9	14.4	4.9	0.35	10	1.60	17.1	0.00
	Max	213.9	129.0	448.9	1.52	60	2.80	23.0	5.90
	Mean	52.6	45.7	59.3	0.74	33	2.22	19.2	3.08
	SD	35.7	25.2	94.7	0.25	14	0.33	1.6	1.39
Summer (Jul.28-A ug.1)	Min	12.2	11.8	4.8	0.27	20	1.80	29.3	0.0
	Max	108.5	94.1	360.7	1.52	70	3.20	32.4	4.90
	Mean	48.4	43.2	50.6	0.71	34	2.47	31.1	3.12
	SD	23.2	19.4	58.1	0.26	12	0.36	1.0	0.97
Autumn (Oct.12-1 5)	Min	10.3	7.9	4.0	0.46	10	1.70	23.0	0.00
	Max	137.0	74.1	246.6	1.52	85	2.90	26.0	5.05
	Mean	31.3	26.0	35.7	0.84	38	2.37	24.3	2.63
	SD	21.0	12.8	46.9	0.20	12	0.30	0.8	1.15

T: water temperature; V: wind velocity; SD – standard deviation

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of tripton, phytoplankton, and CDOM and total absorption coefficients (lines represent different sites and cruises).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Temporal and Spatial Variations in Optically Active Substances

There was a large variation in concentrations of the three optically active substances (TSM, Chla, and CDOM) and other indexes (Table I), both within and between seasons,

reflecting the temporal–spatial heterogeneousness of the large shallow lake.

The TSM concentration was significantly higher in winter than in other three seasons (ANOVA analysis, $p < 0.001$). In contrast, Chla concentration was significantly lower in winter than in the other three seasons (ANOVA analysis, $p < 0.001$), corresponding to the absence and presence of marked algal blooms. Although there was no marked algal bloom in winter, Chla concentration was still relatively high, with a mean value of $16.5 \pm 6.6 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, demonstrating that Lake Taihu was a highly eutrophic lake. The mean values of TSM, tripton, and aCDOM(440) in winter were 2.95, 3.35, and 1.29 times of those in other three seasons, respectively. However, the mean value of Chla in winter was 0.34 times of that in other three seasons.

Some spatial differences were found for concentrations of optically active substances. Overall, the concentrations of the three optically active substances were higher in Meiliang Bay and the north of the lake than in the south. The mean concentrations of Chla and CDOM in transects 1, 2, and 3 were significantly higher than those in transect 4 (ANOVA analysis, $p < 0.001$) in all four seasons. However, the mean concentration of TSM did not differ significantly among the four transects in any season.

In summer and autumn, concentrations of TSM and Chla were significantly higher in Meiliang Bay and the northern lake regions where serious algal blooms occurred. In contrast, in spring, the highest concentration of Chla was in the southwest of the lake, near sites 39 and 40, where an intense algal bloom occurred.

In winter, the Chla concentration remained at a relative low level for the whole lake as compared to other three seasons. In winter, the overall TSM concentrations were relatively high, due to deformation and disappearance of submerged aquatic vegetation and the marked sediment resuspension caused by the significant wind-induced wave action prior to the sampling dates. The mean wind velocity on January 4, 5, and 6 were 7.2, 5.6, and 6.6 $\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, respectively, based on the automatic anemometer measurement of every 10 min in Taihu Lake Laboratory Ecosystem Research Station, which was located in the littoral of

Lake Taihu.

In winter, there was no correlation between CTSM and CChla; however, in the other three seasons, there was a significant positive correlation ($p < 0.001$). This suggests that the interdependence between TSM and Chla was quite strong in spring, summer, and autumn due to the frequent algal blooms which have a large contribution to TSM. TSM contained both organic and inorganic particles. For those with algal bloom, TSM contained a large amount organic matter in addition to the inorganic matter.

B Variation in Absorption Coefficients

Fig. 3. (left) Mean absorption spectra of tripton ($a_d(\lambda)$), phytoplankton ($a_{ph}(\lambda)$), and CDOM ($a_{CDOM}(\lambda)$) and (right) specific absorption coefficient spectra of tripton ($a_d^*(\lambda)$)

The spectral absorption coefficients of tripton, phytoplankton, CDOM, and the total absorption coefficient are shown in Fig. 2.

The absorption coefficient of CDOM approached zero near 700 nm and increased exponentially with decreasing wavelength over the 350–700-nm range. In previous studies, hyperbolic fitting has been suggested as a better approach than linear fitting [12], [28]. Thus, in this paper, hyperbolic fitting was used to fit CDOM spectra for wavelengths of 300–600 nm, considering that the CDOM absorption coefficient was near zero or negative over a wavelength range larger than 600 nm. The mean and standard deviation of the spectral slope (S) for CDOM absorption were 6.36 and 0.83 nm⁻¹, respectively, based on the 197 data points (50 sites × 4 seasons – 3 points with high Chla). These values for the whole year were very close to the values for winter and summer [12]. Therefore, CDOM absorption can be expressed by

$$a_{\text{CDOM}}(\lambda) = a_{\text{CDOM}}(440)(\lambda/440)^{-6.36}. \quad (16)$$

The absorption coefficient of tripton decreased with increasing wavelength in all four seasons (Fig. 2). Many studies have shown that tripton has relatively stable absorption characteristics, which can be described using an exponential function [29], [30]. Considering that the absorption spectral shape of CDOM and tripton was very similar in this paper, a hyperbolic fit of the tripton absorption spectra was performed. Based on a large data set of 727 samples, collected from different regions of Lake Taihu from July 2004 to April 2007, it was found that the hyperbolic model was more accurate in its representation of the tripton absorption than the simple exponential model (unpublished data). The range of spectral slope values (S_d) for tripton in the wavelength range 400 – 700 nm in this paper, using hyperbolic fitting, was relatively narrow from 4.96 to 7.50 nm^{-1} , with a mean value of 6.27 nm^{-1} and a coefficient of variation of 6.1%. The mean values of the spectral slopes of CDOM (6.36 nm^{-1}) and tripton (6.27 nm^{-1}) were very close. For all four seasons, tripton absorption can be expressed as follows:

$$a_d(\lambda) = a_d(440)(\lambda/440)^{-6.27}. \quad (17)$$

The absorption spectra of phytoplankton showed that the pigments had two diagnostic absorption peaks, in the blue wavelength (approximately 440 nm) and in the red wavelength (approximately 675 nm) (Fig. 2). However, the absorption coefficients of phytoplankton varied significantly in space and time because of marked differences in pigment concentrations. Phytoplankton absorption was very high at some sites during the algal blooms in spring, summer, and autumn.

Fig. 4. Remote-sensing reflectance in four different seasons (lines represent different sites.)

Fig. 5. Comparison of measured and modeled remote-sensing reflectance just above the water surface $R_{RS}(\lambda, 0^+)$ from two sites in July 2006.

Fig. 6. Position of remote-sensing reflectance peak near 700 nm versus Chla concentrations.

Total absorption spectra were very similar to those of tripton, decreasing from 400 to 600 nm, except for several sites that had serious algal blooms on the water surface (Fig. 2), indicating the strong absorption by tripton in this shallow lake with its high tripton

concentration (7.9–281.7 mg · L⁻¹). The mean absorption of tripton, phytoplankton, and CDOM also showed that tripton dominated the total absorption spectra [Fig. 3(a)]. Specific absorption spectra of phytoplankton in this paper fell within the range found in a range of water bodies [29], [31] but with a relatively low value as compared to the clear oceanic waters due to high Chla concentration in Lake Taihu [Fig. 3(b)]. Specific absorption coefficient of phytoplankton has a tendency to decrease with increasing Chla concentration due to the so-called package effect. The mean value of ad(443) of 0.057 m² · g⁻¹ was higher than the one of 0.041 m² · g⁻¹ obtained by Babin et al. [31]. The difference can be partly attributed to the different calculation method. We note that Babin et al. [31] calculated specific absorption coefficient of tripton using TSM concentration (including phytoplankton). However, we calculated tripton concentration by excluding phytoplankton. This effect is expected to be the most important in eutrophic Lake Taihu where phytoplankton represents an important fraction of TSM during algal bloom in summer.

Furthermore, the difference in the sources and mineral composition for coastal and lake waters may also cause the difference in a*d(443).

Fig. 7. Retrieval model of Chla concentration and comparison of measured and estimated values using the three-band reflectance model (37.3% in the bracket is the percentage of RMSE accounting for the mean C_{Chla}).

Fig. 6. Position of remote-sensing reflectance peak near 700 nm versus Chla concentrations.

C. Modeling of Remote-Sensing Reflectance

For each station, the above-water remote-sensing reflectance was modeled according to (12) and (13). The total absorption and backscattering were taken from the measured inherent optical properties and application of (4), (8), (9), and (10).

The seasonal variation in remote-sensing reflectance is shown in Fig. 4. The large variability in the concentration of the three optically active substances and in their inherent optical properties resulted in large spatial and temporal variabilities in the magnitude of the modeled remote-sensing reflectance spectra. The reflectance spectra were highly variable at different sites and seasons. To validate the modeled $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0+)$, Fig. 5 shows the comparison of measured and modeled $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0+)$ at two typical sites in July 2006. There was a very good match of the measured and modeled $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0+)$, suggesting that it was reasonable and feasible to model remote-sensing reflectance based on the measurements of

the beam-attenuation coefficient and the absorption coefficient in the laboratory. However, the

$R_{rs}(\lambda,0^+)$ modeled was generally lower than the measured value at shorter wavelengths, less than 550 nm; this error being attributed to the uncertainty of scattering and backscattering coefficients. The scattering coefficient was calculated from beam-attenuation and absorption coefficients measurement made with a spectrophotometer (8), and since the spectrophotometer had an acceptance angle of 5° , some backscattered radiation was lost. Because the backscattering coefficient increased with decreasing wavelength, this loss term is greater at shorter wavelengths, causing the modeled $R_{rs}(\lambda,0^+)$ to be generally lower than the measured value. The difference in measured and modeled $R_{rs}(\lambda,0^+)$ could also have arisen from the errors in the observed $R_{rs}(\lambda,0^+)$. Although the water was placid in most cases, the potential for error due to skylight reflection still existed. Furthermore, the reflectance of air–water interface, which was slightly dependent on wind waves and set as a constant in this paper, induced a potential error. These modeled spectra were very close in magnitude, shape, and spectral features to the typical reflectance spectra previously measured in Lake Taihu [14]. Remote-sensing reflectance is proportional to the ratio of spectral backscattering to the sum of spectral absorption and backscattering of all optically active substances (12). Spectral reflectance peaks and local minima were generally inversely related to the total absorption spectra. In general, reflectance peaks occurred at around 560, 650, and 700 nm (Figs. 4 and 5). Reflectance minima occurred at short wavelengths near 400 nm due to strong absorption by particulate and dissolved substances (Fig. 2) and near 800 nm due to pure-water absorption. As the modeled reflectance spectra were calculated from the measured absorption and backscattering coefficients, the effect of bottom reflectance to the total reflectance was eliminated. However, the bottom reflectance might affect the in situ measured reflectance, particularly in the typical macrophyte-dominated regions (Xukou Bay and East Lake Taihu) [11]. For example, previous studies [13], [32] got the significant error of Chla concentration and

water quality in the two bays (Xukou Bay and East Lake Taihu) based on in situ measured and remotely derived $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^+)$.

In turbid Lake Taihu, absorption by dissolved organic matter and tripton and scattering by particulate matter contributed most to reflectance in the range of 400–500 nm, and a common characteristic of reflectance spectra in this range was low sensitivity to the variation of Chla concentration. As a result, the blue-to-green ratio $R_{rs}(440)/R_{rs}(550)$ could not be used to estimate CChla in waters studied. Therefore, the difference in measured and modeled $R_{rs}(\lambda, 0^+)$ at short wavelengths had no effect on CChla estimation in Lake Taihu. A peak in the green range near 550–570 nm (Figs. 4 and 5) was due to the minimal absorption of all algal pigments (Fig. 2), and scattering by ISM and phytoplankton cells controlled the magnitude of reflectance in this range. At around 675 nm, the reflectance minimum was due to phytoplankton absorption, particularly in sites with high pigment concentration. However, reflectance in this range was strongly affected by tripton concentration, in addition to Chla concentration in turbid Lake Taihu, which decreased the correlation between $R_{rs}(675)$ and CChla. A local minimum around 625 nm was due to phycocyanin absorption. This pigment is present primarily in cyanobacteria, and thus, a local reflectance minimum at 625 nm has often been used to monitor cyanobacterial blooms in eutrophic lakes [8], [9].

A marked peak was recorded near 700 nm, which corresponded to the decrease of particle scattering and the increase of pure-water absorption. The position of this peak shifted toward longer wavelengths with increasing Chla concentration. Fig. 6 shows that peak position was closely related to CChla concentration. This shows that, in addition to Chla absorption, scattering by tripton played a significant role in controlling reflectance in this spectral region. The red-shifting of the reflectance peak position near 700 nm with increasing Chla concentration was observed in other productive turbid waters [33], [34].

Our measurements in Lake Taihu were performed over a wide range of biooptical characteristics of water in different seasons at different solar zenith angles (ranging from

15° to 77°). However, the standard deviation of the f/Q values estimated was less than 2.5%, with a mean f/Q value of 0.1553, which was very close to the value reported in Case-1 waters [35]. Although both f and Q were largely dependent on solar zenith angle and the inherent optical properties of water, f/Q was basically independent of solar zenith angle. These results suggest that, for the nadir viewing the geometry of our measurements in these Case-2 waters, the observed variability in the quantity f/Q was not very large and not markedly different from Case-1 waters.

D. Retrieval Model of Chla

Obtaining accurate information on the temporal-spatial variation of Chla

concentration and algal blooms in Lake Taihu is critical for water-quality monitoring, understanding the mechanisms of eutrophication, and for issuing warnings to safeguard the drinking-water plants surrounding Lake Taihu. However, the application of currently operational satellite Chla algorithms, such as MERIS, in the extremely turbid waters of Lake Taihu often results in erroneous retrievals.

In previous studies of Lake Taihu, single-band, band-ratio, and one-order derivative methods were used to estimate CChla [13], [14]. In contrast, in this paper, a three-band reflectance model was used to estimate CChla under conditions of high turbidity and high algal biomass. This model was tested on its accuracy and ability to perform for all seasons. Recently, a conceptual model containing remote-sensing reflectance in three spectral bands in the red and near-infrared (NIR) range of the spectrum was suggested for retrieving Chla in turbid productive waters [33], [34], [36]

$$\text{Chla} = A \times [R_{\text{rs}}^{-1}(\lambda_1) - R_{\text{rs}}^{-1}(\lambda_2)] \times R_{\text{rs}}(\lambda_3) + B \quad (18)$$

The three-band reflectance model was originally developed for estimating pigment contents in terrestrial vegetation. Reciprocal reflectance in the first spectral band λ_1 should be most sensitive to CChla. $R_{\text{rs}}(\lambda_1)$ is also affected by absorption by tripton, CDOM, and water as well as backscattering by all particulate matter. The effect of backscattering and the absorption by tripton and CDOM can be minimized using a second spectral band, where $R_{\text{rs}}(\lambda_2)$ is minimally sensitive to absorptions by phytoplankton, tripton, and CDOM. $R_{\text{rs}}(\lambda_3)$ is minimally affected by phytoplankton, tripton, and CDOM, and the total absorption the third band is a measure of the absorption by water. Based on these assumptions, the spectral ranges of three bands are restricted to 660–690, 700–750, and 730–750 nm, respectively. We refer to Dall’Olmo and Gitelson [36] and Gitelson et al. [34] for a detailed description and explanation of this choice of bands. Some studies showed that the three-spectral-band reflectance model $[R_{\text{rs}}^{-1}(\lambda_1) - R_{\text{rs}}^{-1}(\lambda_2)] \times R_{\text{rs}}(\lambda_3)$ was more precise than the band-ratio method.

In order to find the best three bands by which to estimate Chla concentration in Lake

Taihu, the combinations of any three wavelengths of λ_1 from 660 to 690 nm, λ_2 from 700 to 750 nm, and λ_3 from 730 to 750 nm were used for correlation with CChla using the remote-sensing reflectance modeled. The optimal band combination was judged by RMSE in this paper. Linear correlation showed that the three-band reflectance model $[R_{rs-1}(690) - R_{rs-1}(703)] \times R_{rs}(759)$ gave the lowest RMSE, the highest correlation coefficient ($r^2 = 0.94$), and estimation precision. The resulting Chla estimation model and the comparison of measured and estimated CChla are shown in Fig. 7. The RMSE and the mean RE were $15.1 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ (37.3% from the mean CChla) and 44.4%, respectively. Although $[R_{rs-1}(690) - R_{rs-1}(703)] \times R_{rs}(759)$ gave the lowest RMSE, the corresponding RE was slightly larger than the lowest value of 42.5%. The measured and estimated values for CChla were distributed along the 1:1 line, indicating that the three-band reflectance model $[R_{rs-1}(690) - R_{rs-1}(703)] \times R_{rs}(759)$ could be used for the eutrophic turbid waters of Lake Taihu.

From (11) and (12), it can be concluded that the error sources for modeled remote-sensing reflectance are derived from the f/Q and the backscattering probability (β). However, for the three-band model, f/Q is independent on the wavelength and will be eliminated in the model, thus has no effect on retrieval precision of CChla. In this paper, the values of 0.012, 0.015, 0.021, and 0.024 (33% standard deviation as compared to 0.018) were used to check the sensitivity of the three-band model to β for Chla retrieval precision. Table II shows the fitting equation, r^2 , RMSE, and RE of CChla estimation using the different β values. The variation of β only had a slight effect on the RMSE and RE of CChla precision. The maximal deviation of RMSE and RE were 1.9% and 2.1%, respectively, using 0.012 as β value as compared to the model using 0.018. Furthermore, the different β value only changed the linear slope but not the intercept of retrieval model. The results suggested that the three-band model developed in this paper was not sensitive to the uncertain parameters and could be used to CChla estimation.

Furthermore, Fig. 8 shows the comparison of measured and modeled $[R_{rs-1}(690) -$

$R_{rs-1}(703)] \times R_{rs}(759)$ in order to further validate the three-band model using the remote-sensing reflectance modeled. Measured and modeled $[R_{rs-1}(690) - R_{rs-1}(703)] \times R_{rs}(759)$ were linked by a highly significant linear relationship ($r^2 = 0.90$), with a slope close to 1.0 (0.935) (Fig. 8). This analysis further showed that the modeled $R_{rs}(\lambda,0+)$ can be used to estimate CChla based on the threeband model as compared to measured $R_{rs}(\lambda,0+)$ spectra in other studies [33], [34], [36].

To compare the precision of the three-band reflectance model with other methods, the band-ratio method was also used to estimate CChla. To find the optimal spectral bands of the bandratio method, the ratios of any two wavelengths from 350 to 800 nm were used for correlation with CChla. Linear correlation showed that the ratio of $R_{rs}(713)/R_{rs}(674)$ gave the highest determination coefficient ($r^2 = 0.92$) and the lowest RMSE ($18.0 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) (Fig. 9). The three-band reflectance model $[R_{rs-1}(690) - R_{rs-1}(703)] \times R_{rs}(759)$ was more precise than the band-ratio method $R_{rs}(713)/R_{rs}(674)$ as has been validated in other Case-2 waters [33], [34]. The three-band model with spectral bands optimized for inland waters, with Chla ranging from 4.4 to 217.3 $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ [36] and from 107 to 3078 $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ [33], allowed accurate estimation of Chla when applied to Lake Taihu, in spite of this lake having a very different composition of optically active substances (Chla, tripton, and CDOM).

β	Retrieval equation*	r^2	RMSE (m^{-1})	RE (%)
0.012	$C_{\text{Chla}}=322.3x+27.6$	0.94	15.4	45.1
0.015	$C_{\text{Chla}}=335.1x+27.6$	0.94	15.2	44.5
0.018	$C_{\text{Chla}}=347.7x+27.6$	0.94	15.1	44.2
0.021	$C_{\text{Chla}}=360.2x+27.6$	0.94	15.0	44.1
0.024	$C_{\text{Chla}}=372.4x+27.6$	0.94	15.0	44.1

*: Here x is $[R_{rs}^{-1}(690)-R_{rs}^{-1}(703)] \times R_{rs}(759)$

E. Retrieval Model Validation

In order to further understand the applicability of the threeband model, we presented the evaluation of the performance of the three-band model using an independent data set including two investigations. CChla ranged from 1.6 to 202.0 $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ with a mean value

of $29.6 \pm 36.6 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, which fell into the range CChla used to develop the model. Comparisons of the measured and estimated CChla by the three-band model and the band-ratio model are shown in Fig. 10. Measured and estimated CChla by the three-band were in good agreement with a highly significant linear relationship ($r^2 = 0.92$ and a slope of 0.967 close to 1.0). The RMSE and percentage of RMSE accounting for the mean CChla of validation data set were lower than those of calibration data set (Figs. 7 and 10), suggesting that the performance of the three-band was accepted. Compared to the three-band model, the performance of the band-ratio method had a larger RMSE and RE (1.45 and 2.01 times of the three-band model, respectively). One of the reasons for the better performance of the three-band model, compared to the band-ratio method, was that the three-band model completely removed interferences due to backscattering by means of $R_{rs}(\lambda_2)$ and $R_{rs}(\lambda_3)$.

The three chosen bands basically fall into the range of MERIS channels (channels 8, 9, and 10: 681/8, 709/10, and 754/8 nm, respectively), which would make it possible to estimate Chla accurately using MERIS imagery. The determination coefficient, RMSE, and the mean RE were 0.92, $17.0 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, and 48.1%, respectively, using the central bands of MERIS imagery $[R_{rs-1}(681) - R_{rs-1}(709)] \times R_{rs}(754)$, which gave high retrieval accuracy.

Although the algorithms presented in this paper are derived for typical band settings of satelliteborne instruments like MERIS, it will still be quite challenging to investigate the applicability in actual MERIS or MODIS images of Lake Taihu. A major source of concern is the robustness of the algorithms for imperfect atmospheric correction over turbid waters [37], [38]. Small errors in the derivation of aerosol loading and the angstrom coefficient at near-IR wavelength typically translated in significant deviation for normalized water-leaving radiance at shorter wavelengths [39]. At present, the blackpixel assumption widely used in Case-1 waters for atmospheric correction was inappropriate in productive Case-2 waters with higher sediment or Chla concentration. However, once the atmospheric

correction procedures over extremely turbid waters have improved, the three-band algorithm might turn out to be a rather robust algorithm for Chla retrieval, because the offsets in the $R_{rs}(\lambda)$, due to errors in the atmospheric correction procedure, are partially counterbalanced by taking Rrs ratio' s in a narrow wavelength interval (681 – 754 nm).

IV. CONCLUSION

Effective remote retrieval of Chla is a major challenge in turbid and eutrophic Case-2 waters such as Lake Taihu in China. Although several previous studies have provided reliable detection of Chla in Case-1 waters, many studies were not able to fully support accurate identification, monitoring, and forecasting of future locations of algal blooms in optically complex Case-2 waters. The retrieval accuracy of Chla in Lake Taihu depends to a large extent on the accuracy of, and consistency among, the in situ data used in the development, validation, and improvement of the applied remote-sensing biooptical algorithms. In this paper, biooptical measurements from four different seasons, with large temporal–spatial variability in the concentration of three optically active substances and inherent optical properties, were used to model the variation of remote-sensing reflectance. We found that the three-band model $[R_{rs}-1(690) - R_{rs}-1(703)] \times R_{rs}(759)$ in the red and NIR wavelengths, where impact from CDOM and tripton absorptions on reflectance was minimal, could be used to retrieve Chla with better performance than the band-ratio method widely used in previous studies. The wavelengths

proposed for the three-band algorithm correspond well to the MERIS bands and provide a good basis for satellite monitoring of phytoplankton blooms in Case-2 waters

from MERIS. It was noteworthy that the three-band model using MERIS central bands $[Rrs-1(681) - Rrs-1(709)] \times Rrs(754)$ also allowed accurate estimation of Chla in the range of Chla from 4.0 to 448.9 $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ from four different seasons, suggesting that MERIS imagery could be used to monitor Chla not only in waters with low-to-moderate Chla concentrations (as has been done in previous studies) but also in extremely turbid and hypereutrophic waters. However, successful application of this algorithm to satellite data depends heavily on the accuracy of the atmospheric correction in the red-NIR region over lakes. This might pose new challenges to the positioning NIR bands in future missions and characterization of land influences on atmospheric correction over relatively small lakes like Lake Taihu.

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